

How Wise is the Crowd?

Bias and Edge in Prediction Markets

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March 2026

Abstract

Prediction markets are increasingly relied upon as real-time probability oracles, yet their predictive signals remain polluted by structural inefficiencies. While prior literature documents anomalies like the favorite-longshot bias at an aggregate level, the microstructural origins of these distortions—specifically *who* generates and exploits them—remain unstudied in modern ecosystems. To investigate this, we engineer a scalable, multi-threaded data architecture capable of synchronously ingesting and persisting tick-level order flow, decentralized wallet histories, and user commentary across Polymarket and Kalshi.

Moving beyond traditional discrete quantile-binning, we introduce a continuous, multivariate framework to isolate aggregate market *bias* from individual trader *edge* across the probability spectrum and contract lifecycle. Our findings challenge the idea that favorite-longshot bias is present in every prediction market. In the markets we find it to be present, such as Mention Markets, the classic favorite-longshot bias is may in fact be a statistical artifact masking a pervasive “Yes Bias” [1], driven by extreme temporal volatility and not controlling for the time to market completion in previous methodologies.

Furthermore, we find that “Whales”, or the most capitalized players, are not the most sophisticated. By dynamically reconstructing participant positions, we demonstrate that Whales, on average, systematically bleed expected value to small-order traders. Rather than acting as sharp informed players, these large actors likely trade on ideological conviction, structurally overpaying for specific narratives and suffering from adverse selection against smaller participants. Utilizing a Natural Language Inference (NLI) stance-detection framework, we see to evident interaction between vocality of a trader and realized market performance. We find no statistically significant correlation between sentiment intensity and informational edge, indicating that the most prominent voices in these ecosystems function primarily as sources of communicative noise.

Ultimately, this research provides a reproducible methodology for actively denoising prediction market probabilities by adjusting for temporal lifecycles, liquidity environments, and the ideological biases held by heavily capitalized, unsophisticated traders.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Prediction markets have emerged as powerful mechanisms for aggregating information about real-world events, transforming dispersed beliefs into continuously updated prices. Rooted in the “wisdom of crowds” principle, these markets are often described as harnessing decentralized information from heterogeneous participants to produce collective probability estimates [2]. Across modern platforms such as Polymarket and Kalshi, events in categories ranging from sports and political elections to financial outcomes serve as the fundamental unit of analysis for traders and researchers alike. Because market prices are commonly interpreted as probabilistic forecasts, prediction markets provide a natural setting for studying questions of efficiency, liquidity, and behavioral influence.

Kalshi and Polymarket represent the two primary pillars of the modern prediction market landscape, though they operate under distinct structural models. Kalshi is a federally regulated U.S. exchange that specializes in “event contracts”, offering a transparent, CFTC-compliant environment for trading on economic indicators and climate outcomes. In contrast, Polymarket operates as a decentralized, blockchain-based platform, leveraging on-chain liquidity to host a vast array of global markets ranging from geopolitical shifts to pop culture. Together, these platforms have transitioned predictive trading from a niche academic interest into a high-volume financial ecosystem, providing the granular data necessary for modern sentiment analysis.

With increasing trading volume and greater mainstream acceptance, modern prediction markets are frequently assumed to be highly efficient sources of “ground truth” due to the sheer number of participants and the rapid integration of information. This growth is highlighted by the recent re-entry of Polymarket into the United States market [3]. Consequently, the integration of prediction market data into traditional finance has accelerated. Hedge funds and sophisticated traders are increasingly relying on these platforms to extract real-time signals and gauge market sentiment [4] [5]. This utility is particularly evident in macroeconomic forecasting; recent research by the Federal Reserve demonstrates that prediction markets offer highly accurate, continuously updated distributional forecasts for FOMC decisions and other key economic indicators [6].

However, beneath the assumption of pure efficiency lies a significant amount of bias. Prior

literature has long documented systematic distortions in betting and prediction markets. For example, Tetlock [7] illustrates how liquidity dynamics can exacerbate deviations of prices from true event probabilities, closely related to the well-known “favorite–longshot bias,” whereby low-probability events are overpriced and high-probability events are underpriced relative to realized outcomes.

Despite these foundational insights, significant research gaps remain. Much of the early literature on the favorite–longshot bias was developed using legacy prediction market platforms, whose market structure, participant composition, and liquidity dynamics differ from those of modern platforms. Although recent studies have examined the bias in modern prediction markets, the rapid evolution of these platforms—particularly with respect to on-chain trading, public position transparency, and retail participation—creates a moving empirical environment. At the same time, collecting comprehensive, event-aligned datasets from these platforms remains difficult and time-consuming. Together, these factors create scope to extend existing work using richer, systematically constructed datasets that reflect the evolving institutional design of modern prediction markets.

Importantly, existing work largely treats bias as an aggregate market-level phenomenon. We instead introduce a participant-level perspective, examining which traders contribute to the bias, which traders systematically exploit it, and how these dynamics evolve over the lifecycle of a market. To our knowledge, this decomposition of bias into its contributing and arbitraging agents across time has not been systematically studied in modern prediction markets.

Finally, prior work largely fails to consider bias on a granular, high-dimensional basis. Modern prediction markets generate a rich layer of user-generated commentary alongside on-chain trading activity. This allows for a novel level of analysis: we can observe exactly *who* has taken positions, how bias changes through time, and how participant position size and volatility interact with price formation and trader edge.

Addressing this research at scale is nontrivial. Accessing historical trades, order book data, event resolution, and user comments in a consistent and reproducible manner requires substantial engineering effort. Platform APIs expose low-level mechanics rather than event-aligned datasets suitable for statistical study. Therefore, rigorous cross-platform analysis of bias dynamics requires a structured data framework capable of integrating and aligning these multidimensional signals across platforms.

1.1 Objectives

The primary objective of this project is to analyze the nuances of mispricing and bias dynamics in modern prediction markets along three dimensions: over the market lifecycle, across price levels, and at the trader level. While prior literature has documented the favorite–longshot bias at the aggregate level, the behavioral and microstructural mechanisms underlying the bias remain insufficiently understood in the context of contemporary prediction markets. By shifting the analytical focus from market-level averages to individual participants, we aim to identify *who* generates the bias and *who* systematically exploits it.

Firstly, we intend to study how market bias dynamics evolve across the normalized lifespan of a contract (from $t = 0$ to $T = 1$) and across the continuous price levels space independently of each other.

To study evolution over the trader level dimension, we seek to isolate the concept of individual trader *Edge* (directional expected value) from aggregate market *Bias* (structural mispricing). We categorize market participants based on position size and commentary behavior. First, we distinguish between Whales and small-order traders according to the size of their positions. Second, we further analyze the sentiment of "vocal" traders, participants who post comments, and the edge associated with their trades. This framework allows us to evaluate whether specific cohorts succumb to the bias or actively harvest it.

Crucially, evaluating these dynamics at scale requires moving beyond static, end-of-day snapshots. Therefore, a foundational objective of this work is to construct a unified, high-performance data engineering pipeline capable of capturing real-time order flow, blockchain-level wallet tracking, and social sentiment. By formalizing data collection through a robust, concurrent architecture, we establish a reproducible and easily extendable framework for cross-platform, play-by-play microstructure analysis on platforms like Polymarket and Kalshi.

1.2 Contributions

This paper makes four primary contributions to the study of prediction markets, market microstructure, and behavioral finance:

1. Tracking the Temporal Evolution of the Favorite-Longshot Bias: To determine if market inefficiencies persist consistently across a contract's lifecycle or are arbitrated away as information integrates, we develop a dynamic framework for measuring efficiency over time. By normalizing the lifespan of varied prediction markets from inception ($t = 0$) to expiration ($T = 1$), we track the aggregate erosion or exacerbation of the favorite-longshot bias. Crucially, establishing this temporal map acts as a control baseline. It allows us to overlay our microstructural cohorts—such as Whales and vocal participants—onto the timeline, revealing whether specific groups actively drive the temporal convergence toward efficiency or merely ride the broader market trend.

2. Deconstructing the Drivers of Market Bias through Wallet-Level Analysis: To understand whether highly-capitalized participants (Whales) actively harvest structural inefficiencies or succumb to them alongside small-order traders, we move beyond aggregated order flow. We implement a chronological play-by-play ledger that reconstructs the complete trading history and net positions of thousands of individual proxy wallets after every execution. By mapping these trades into dynamic deciles, we isolate Whale behavior from small-order traders. This granular approach allows us to cleanly separate market-wide *Bias* from individual trader *Edge*, revealing the precise microstructural forces that create and correct mispricing.

3. Quantifying Directional Stance via Natural Language Inference: To investigate the relationship between public discourse and informational edge, we implement a novel stance-detection framework grounded in Natural Language Inference (NLI). Moving beyond traditional polarity-based sentiment analysis, we utilize a cross-encoder *DeBERTa-v3* architecture to evaluate the logical relationship between unstructured trader commentary (premise) and potential market resolutions (hypotheses). By segmenting trading cohorts through this structurally-grounded vocality, we empirically determine whether vocal participants are merely contributing to social noise or if their public assertions signal genuine, unpriced alpha.

4. A High-Performance, Cross-Platform Data Architecture: We introduce a custom-built, multi-threaded tracking engine designed to ingest, normalize, and persist streaming data from Polymarket and Kalshi. Overcoming the fragmented nature and data density of platform APIs, our system utilizes asynchronous WebSocket streams, dynamic Exponential Moving Average (EMA) batching, and a flexible persistence layer (supporting both Single-Writer SQLite Multiton and WAL-Mode multithreading). This point-and-shoot framework enables large-scale, reproducible data collection that captures every tick, trade, and comment.

1.3 Key Findings

Through our granular, participant-level analysis across Polymarket and Kalshi, we uncover several structural realities that challenge the assumption of prediction market efficiency. Our key findings are as follows:

- **The Apparent Illusion of the Favorite-Longshot Bias:** Our preliminary univariate analysis suggested the presence of a classic favorite-longshot bias in Mention Markets. However, by deploying multivariate penalized splines to control for the confounding effects of contract lifecycle timing, we reveal this to be a statistical artifact. Instead, these markets exhibit a pervasive “Yes Bias,” whereby participants consistently overpay for the “Yes” outcome — that is, the contract that pays off if the reference event occurs — relative to the corresponding “No” outcome.
- **Efficiency is Regime-Dependent:** Aggregate market efficiency varies drastically by the underlying subject matter. While short-duration 15M Crypto Markets exhibit a mean bias near zero, they obscure volatile, offsetting inefficiencies. Conversely, sports markets (NBA) exhibit structural underpricing in mid-tier probabilities that perfectly collapses to zero efficiency exclusively when the matchup is perceived as a true coin-flip ($P = 0.5$).
- **The Temporal Decay of Edge:** The informational alpha (edge) possessed by aggressive liquidity takers is not static. In Mention Markets, taker edge is highly positive during the active lifespan of the contract—indicating effective live-information integration—but collapses sharply as the contract nears expiration ($t \rightarrow 1.0$) and certainty becomes ubiquitous.
- **Whales Succumb to Adverse Selection:** Contrary to traditional financial intu-

ition, which assumes capital dominance correlates with informational advantage, we find that directional edge systematically *decays* as participant size increases. Highly capitalized participants (Whales) consistently exhibit the lowest relative edge, suffering from severe negative edge in Mention Markets. This evidence indicates that whales are consistently outperformed by small-order traders.

- **Relationship Between Edge And Trader Vocality:** We find no statistically significant correlation between sentiment intensity and informational edge, indicating that the most prominent voices in these ecosystems function primarily as sources of communicative noise.

Chapter 2

Background Knowledge and Related Work

2.1 What are Prediction Markets?

Prediction markets are markets that allow traders to bet on the occurrence of future events by buying and selling contracts that resolve to \$1 if the event occurs, or \$0 if the event doesn't. Popular online prediction market platforms such as Polymarket and Kalshi host prediction markets on a diverse range of topics, from sports to politics (e.g. election winners) to financial events such as daily S&P 500 close values or corporate earnings, or even more niche events like how many tweets Elon Musk will make in the next 2 weeks. Because contract prices are constrained between \$0 and \$1, they are widely interpreted as the market's implied probability of the outcome. For example, if a "Yes" contract for a specific team winning a sports game trades at \$0.82, market participants are effectively pricing an 82% probability of that victory.

To formalize the structure of these platforms, we begin with the concept of a **series**, which represents a broad collection of related events. An **event** is defined as a collection of one or more related (though not necessarily mutually exclusive) **markets**. While prices are not assigned to events themselves, they are assigned to individual markets, which represent specific bets on future outcomes of real-world "reference events". Each market consists of two mutually exclusive **outcomes**—often "Yes" and "No"—and participants may buy or sell contracts for either, via market or limit orders. Since the price of a market is bounded between \$0 and \$1, the relationship between outcomes is defined by:

$$\text{Price}_{\text{Outcome A}} = 1 - \text{Price}_{\text{Outcome B}}$$

Consequently, buying Outcome A is both semantically and mechanically equivalent to selling Outcome B.

For instance, within an NBA series, a single event might be the Nets vs. Celtics game on Feb. 27, 2026. This event may comprise multiple markets, such as the winner of the game (with outcomes "Nets" and "Celtics") or whether a specific player scores above a certain

2.1. WHAT ARE PREDICTION MARKETS?

point threshold. If the “Nets” outcome trades at \$0.30, the “Celtics” outcome must trade at \$0.70. Once a market is **resolved** based on the final result of the reference event, the winning outcome settles to \$1 and the losing outcome to \$0. Other event examples include financial benchmarks, such as the S&P 500 closing price at the end of 2026, where each of its markets represent the close price being within certain ranges.

For each event/market, participants can see publicly on platform websites current and historical traded prices of each outcome, current L2 order book snapshots, and trade activity. A characteristic unique to Polymarket and Kalshi is that for every event, market participants can leave comments that are tagged with their current positions in the markets. User profiles are also public, and document user P&L, positions, and trades. In addition to the aforementioned data, historical order book snapshots per market are also retrievable programmatically. Furthermore, because Polymarket operates natively on the Polygon blockchain, executed trades are recorded as public blockchain transactions and settled by smart contracts. Thus, trade data that can be fetched from the Polymarket API can be verified and further enriched by on-chain data, which is public. Kalshi, by contrast, is a centralized CFTC-regulated exchange where order matching and settlement occur off-chain within the exchange’s internal systems.

Figure 2.1: Screenshot of a Polymarket Event

Figure 2.2: Screenshot of a Kalshi Event

The lifecycle of a prediction market follows a standard progression: upon creation, the market **opens** and enters a trading period where participants exchange contracts. Shortly after the market **closes** (trading stops) and the real-world outcome is determined, a resolution price is established (i.e. the market is **resolved**), and the final payouts are distributed to all market participants.

2.2 Related Literature

This paper makes contributions to three primary bodies of literature: the forecasting accuracy of prediction markets, the behavioral and structural drivers of the favorite-longshot bias, and the application of machine learning (ML) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) to assess the impact of social and vocal signals on trading behavior.

The foundational evidence for prediction market accuracy stems from the early Iowa Electronic Markets (IEM). Forsythe et al. [8] first demonstrated that computer-mediated markets could outperform opinion polls in predicting election outcomes. This accuracy was subsequently validated by numerous researchers [9, 10, 11], who found impressive long run predictive performance and found it outperformed traditional financial models and ML methods.

Modern iterations of these platforms have only solidified this utility. Swanson, Wang, and Wu [12] analyze how monetary policy announcements are immediately incorporated into Kalshi’s macroeconomic event contracts. Building on this, Diercks, Katz, and Wright [6] from the Federal Reserve Board demonstrate that Kalshi provides a high-frequency, “distributionally rich” benchmark that is valuable for both policymakers and researchers. They find that Kalshi’s median and mode forecasts possess a near-perfect predictive record on the day before FOMC meetings, representing a statistically significant improvement over fed funds futures. Furthermore, their analysis shows that for headline CPI, Kalshi expectations offer a significant improvement over the Bloomberg consensus forecast, illustrating the platform’s ability to resolve uncertainty and capture asymmetric responses to news in real-time. This predictive power is echoed by Berging [13], who argues that scalable markets like Kalshi provide “meta-signals”—wealth-weighted aggregations of information that are largely orthogonal to other data sources and capable of outperforming standard statistical models. Our work builds on this foundation by studying the behavior and accuracy of prediction market prices across market lifecycle stages, price levels, and participant categories.

Despite their forecasting power, prediction markets are not immune to structural noise. The favorite-longshot bias—a well-documented empirical regularity where low-probability events (“longshots”) are systematically overvalued and high-probability events (“favorites”) are undervalued—remains a central focus of behavioral finance. While prior literature often attributes favorite-longshot bias to psychological factors like risk-seeking behavior or probability misperceptions [7] [11], Whelan [14] provides a structural explanation: commercial fee models act as an implicit driver of favorite-longshot bias. Because fees are proportionately larger relative to the cost of a longshot contract than a favorite, the post-fee loss rates depend negatively on the probability of the event being backed.

Recent literature has also focused on market microstructure and the institutional design of modern exchanges to explain pricing anomalies. Burgi et al. [15] provide the first systematic evidence on Kalshi, highlighting its unique quote-driven microstructure where “Makers” accept trades from “Takers.” They find that Makers generally earn higher returns, suggesting an informational edge among liquidity providers. Conversely, on decentralized platforms, Reichenbach and Walther [16] find no evidence of a general, market-wide favorite-longshot bias. Instead, they document a pronounced “default bias” or “Yes bias,” consistent with status quo bias and the asymmetric framing of “Yes” options on user interfaces. They further show that while only 30% of traders are profitable, the persistence of their gains suggests the existence of genuine skill, potentially derived from exploiting the biases of less-skilled “noise” traders.

While these studies provide valuable platform-level insights, they largely observe aggregate symptoms rather than individual causes. Determining whether inefficiencies like the favorite-longshot bias are driven by structural design, irrational risk-seeking behaviours, or asymmetric information requires moving beyond market-wide averages. To move past theoretical assumptions, it is necessary to study this phenomenon at the individual participant level. Our research addresses this gap by proposing a wallet-level methodology that isolates specific user cohorts, allowing us to observe exactly who generates and who exploits these biases over the contract lifecycle.

To fully understand the behavioral mechanics of these traders, financial research has increasingly pivoted towards interpretable machine learning to extract structured insights from unstructured qualitative data. In traditional finance, Bell et al. develop methods to understand and interpret complex machine learning outcomes in a variety of ways [17, 18]. This ranges from a framework to embed equalized-odds fairness directly into estimations to produce legally compliant feature contributions for mortgage lending, to “Glass Box” models for corporate bonds that match black-box accuracy while identifying the specific macroeconomic shocks driving returns.

Generative AI and Large Language Models (LLMs) have further accelerated the ability to quantify complex narratives. This includes measuring “Creative Destruction” via technological overlaps [19], decoding the Federal Reserve’s inflation attributions from decades of FOMC minutes [20], and using neural networks to reveal systemic gender citation gaps in innovation by controlling for text-based content quality [21]. However, Fedyk et al. [22] caution that default AI agents may harbor demographic perception biases that require mitigation through seeded prompting. These advancements are complemented by theoretical models of “Word of Mouth” information diffusion in social networks [23]. Unlike most financial environments, prediction markets reveal a user’s exact trading position alongside their sentiment, allowing for a direct, data-driven investigation into the alignment between a participant’s public narrative and their actual capital allocation. We extend this body of machine learning research by employing a Natural Language Inference (NLI) model to study the “vocality” of prediction market participants, where vocality is defined as the expression of strong sentiment in public comments.

Chapter 3

Research

3.1 Data Collected

We collected data on 15-minute cryptocurrency markets (e.g. “Will Bitcoin be up or down in the next 15 minutes?”) on Polymarket and Kalshi. On Polymarket only, we also collected longer-dated events such as NBA games and Mention Markets (e.g. “What will Amazon say during their next earnings call?”, or “What will Trump say during Fox News interview on Tuesday?”). A total of 5456 markets’ historical trades and order book snapshots were collected across these platforms. Additionally, user comments on the 5108 Polymarket markets were collected (and not programmatically retrievable for Kalshi). Only markets that started after a particular date and resolved by a certain date were collected, as documented by Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Number of Markets by Platform and Category

Platform	Market Category	Number of Markets	Start Date After	Resolved By
Polymarket	Mention Markets	970	1 Oct 2025	19 Feb 2026
Polymarket	NBA	3,278	1 Nov 2025	17 Feb 2026
Polymarket	Crypto 15M	860	1 Oct 2025	17 Feb 2026
Polymarket Total		5,108		
Kalshi	Crypto 15M	348	22 Feb 2026	23 Feb 2026
Kalshi Total		348		

3.2 Presence of Favorite-Longshot Bias

Prediction markets are often hailed as efficient information aggregators. Nevertheless, they exhibit the persistent favorite–longshot bias, a long-standing empirical regularity in betting markets characterized by the systematic overpricing of low-probability outcomes (“longshots”) and underpricing of high-probability outcomes (“favorites”).

The original study into favorite-longshot bias by Tetlock [7] was conducted in the context of the Tradesports prediction market, which operated in a markedly different technological and regulatory environment. In contrast, modern prediction markets such as Polymarket and Kalshi exist in a significantly more mature ecosystem characterized by widespread internet access, rapid information dissemination through social media, and substantially lower barriers to participation.

These developments have led to a considerable increase in the number and diversity of market participants, as well as higher trading activity and liquidity. A direct comparison of participation, volume, and accessibility metrics across these periods is therefore essential to contextualize any differences in observed market behavior.

Data Pre-Processing

Our empirical analysis spans a broad cross-section of markets across Polymarket and Kalshi. To ensure data quality and comparability, we impose several liquidity and microstructure-based filters. Specifically, we exclude observations which meet any of the following criteria

1. Bid-ask spreads greater than \$0.10
2. Average order book depth below \$10
3. Cumulative trading volume below \$10

Where order book depth is defined as the average of total buy and sell limit order quantities within a \$0.05 band around the mid-price, computed from Level 2 (L2) order book snapshots. All subsequent analysis is conducted on this filtered dataset.

$$\text{Depth}_t = \frac{1}{2} \left(\sum_{i \in \mathcal{B}_t} q_i + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{A}_t} q_j \right),$$

$$\mathcal{B}_t = \{i : p_i^{\text{bid}} \in [m_t - 0.05, m_t]\}, \quad \mathcal{A}_t = \{j : p_j^{\text{ask}} \in [m_t, m_t + 0.05]\},$$

$$m_t = \frac{p_t^{\text{best bid}} + p_t^{\text{best ask}}}{2}.$$

As a validation step, we examine standard microstructure relationships. Consistent with established financial intuition, we observe that tighter bid-ask spreads are associated with higher cumulative trading volume, and that trading volume is positively correlated with order book depth. These relationships provide a useful benchmark and suggest that the markets under consideration exhibit internally consistent liquidity dynamics. Figure 3.1 quantifies this relationship with a correlation heatmap between these metrics.

Figure 3.1: Correlation heatmap of bid-ask spread, cumulative volume, and order book depth.

Summary statistics, including the total number of order book observations and average spread levels, are reported in Table 3.2 and 3.3 below.

Table 3.2: Polymarket Summary Statistics

	All	15M Crypto	NBA	Mention Markets
Ln(Spread) – Ln(Depth)	-0.215	-0.326	-0.456	-0.406
Ln(Spread) – Ln(Volume)	-0.058	0.007	-0.237	-0.241
Ln(Depth) – Ln(Volume)	0.435	0.044	0.359	0.363
Equal-weighted Spread	0.014	0.013	0.015	0.028
Equal-weighted Depth	35,978.021	5,467.128	113,075.642	1,016.731
Equal-weighted Volume	402,775.067	117,360.865	1,124,168.761	7,984.485
Number of Observations	2,242,493	1,604,868	635,899	1,726
Number of Markets	2,320	622	1,611	87

Table 3.3: Kalshi 15M Crypto Markets Summary Statistics

Kalshi 15M Crypto	
Ln(Spread) – Ln(Depth)	-0.312
Ln(Spread) – Ln(Volume)	-0.231
Ln(Depth) – Ln(Volume)	0.613
Equal-weighted Spread	0.020
Equal-weighted Depth	6,445.682
Equal-weighted Volume	26,233.508
Number of Observations	4,753,776
Number of Markets	253

Methodology

Our analysis is grounded in the probability weighting framework of Kahneman and Tversky [24], with a formal foundation provided by Prelec [25]. This literature predicts an S-shaped distortion in subjective probabilities, with a fixed point around $1/e \approx 0.37$, such that low-probability events are systematically overweighted and high-probability events are underweighted. This behavioral prediction provides a theoretical basis for the presence of longshot and favorite bias in prediction markets.

To test this implication in modern markets, we partition prices into five equally spaced intervals of width 0.2, corresponding to probability bins

$$\text{Probability Bins} = (0, 0.2), [0.2, 0.4), [0.4, 0.6), [0.6, 0.8), [0.8, 1)$$

For each bin, we compute average returns to expiration, allowing us to examine how realized outcomes relate to implied probabilities across the distribution. The distribution of these results based on our data are as shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Average Polymarket Markets returns to expiration across probability bins.

Figure 3.3: Average Kalshi 15M Crypto Market returns to expiration across probability bins.

From the preliminary visual, we can see that the ideal S-shape does not hold in most Poly-market markets except for Mention Markets. With this information, we further run more statistical tests to infer how significant this is and how other factors affect this as well

Wald Test

To formally assess the presence of favorite-longshot bias, we implement Wald tests based on returns to expiration across the defined price bins. The null hypothesis of market efficiency is that expected returns are zero across all bins, i.e., prices are unbiased predictors of outcomes.

Let $\text{Price}_1, \dots, \text{Price}_5$ denote the estimated average returns corresponding to the five price bins. The alternative hypothesis, motivated by the favorite-longshot bias literature, is that low-probability events (first two bins, i.e. events with probabilities less than 40%) are overpriced, yielding negative returns, while high-probability events (last three bins, i.e. events with probabilities greater than or equal to 40%) are underpriced, yielding positive returns.

We implement the following Wald tests:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\text{Price}_1 + \text{Price}_2}{2} &= 0 \\ \frac{\text{Price}_3 + \text{Price}_4 + \text{Price}_5}{3} &= 0 \\ \frac{\text{Price}_3 + \text{Price}_4 + \text{Price}_5}{3} - \frac{\text{Price}_1 + \text{Price}_2}{2} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

The first test evaluates whether longshots are overpriced on average, the second assesses whether favorites are underpriced, and the third serves as the primary test of favorite-longshot bias by comparing the two groups directly. Rejection of the third null hypothesis, combined with negative (positive) average returns for low- (high-) probability bins, provides evidence consistent with the presence of favorite-longshot bias.

Regressions

All regressions are estimated using ordinary least squares with dummy variables corresponding to each price bin. Standard errors are clustered at the expiration-date level to account for cross-sectional dependence across observations tied to the same event resolution. This clustering is essential, as information arrival and price convergence are concentrated around the final trading day, leading to correlated residuals within expiration cohorts.

Finally, we note that while bid-ask spreads are broadly present across all markets, liquidity—measured through depth and trading volume—varies significantly across categories. This heterogeneity motivates further analysis of how market-specific liquidity conditions interact with the observed bias patterns.

Bid-ask spreads are broadly comparable in scale across market categories, allowing for the use of common thresholds that produce well-populated bins across all markets. Accordingly, we partition spreads using fixed intervals (≤ 0.01 , $0.01-0.03$, $0.03-0.05$, and > 0.05).

In contrast, liquidity measures such as cumulative trading volume and order book depth exhibit substantial heterogeneity across market categories. As a result, applying common thresholds would lead to sparsely populated or empty bins in certain categories. To address this, we construct quartiles separately within each category, ensuring balanced observations across bins and improving the reliability of the analysis.

Results and Analysis

Liquidity-Agnostic Results

The tables 3.4 and 3.4 report regression results testing the Wald null hypotheses for the presence of favorite-longshot bias. Coefficients are estimated by regressing price-bin indicators on subsequent returns for each contract. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table 3.4: Polymarket Longshot Bias Regression Results

	15M Crypto	Mention-Markets	NBA	All
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	0.003112 (-0.022960)	-0.024657*** (-0.004003)	-0.051516* (-0.026759)	-0.010841 (-0.018461)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	0.007625 (-0.030268)	-0.244861*** (-0.013561)	0.035848 (-0.079088)	0.018387 (-0.034098)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	-0.007909 (-0.024097)	-0.348679*** (-0.103954)	0.016040 (-0.045462)	-0.001517 (-0.021201)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	-0.004671 (-0.031691)	0.096698* (-0.058323)	0.065617 (-0.057223)	0.013796 (-0.027366)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	0.018018 (-0.015513)	0.060099** (-0.028132)	0.055465 (-0.037925)	0.026474* (-0.014806)
Small Probabilities	0.005369 (-0.024077)	-0.134759*** (-0.007535)	-0.007834 (-0.048411)	0.003773 (-0.023190)
Large Probabilities	0.001812 (-0.020568)	-0.063961* (-0.038277)	0.045707 (-0.033937)	0.012918 (-0.017188)
Large – Small	-0.003556 (-0.026321)	0.070798* (-0.041109)	0.053541 (-0.062958)	0.009144 (-0.026956)
R^2	0.000418	0.188797	0.005638	0.000763
Expiration Days	110	15	38	119
Observations	1,604,868	1,726	635,899	2,242,493

Notes: This table reports regression coefficients from tests of the favorite-longshot bias across price bins. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

It is to be noted that from the above results, we observe significant favorite-longshot bias only in the mention-markets traded on Polymarket while the other markets do not reflect this inefficient behavior. Let us further analyse how this effect pans out using another liquidity dimension as a metric

Table 3.5: Kalshi 15M Crypto Longshot Bias Regression Results

	Kalshi 15M Crypto	All
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	-0.031990 (-0.032486)	-0.031990 (-0.032486)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	-0.089313 (-0.063287)	-0.089313 (-0.063287)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	-0.107468*** (-0.040628)	-0.107468*** (-0.040628)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	-0.079555*** (-0.013331)	-0.079555*** (-0.013331)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	-0.009038*** (-0.000301)	-0.009038*** (-0.000301)
Small Probabilities	-0.060651 (-0.047887)	-0.060651 (-0.047887)
Large Probabilities	-0.065353*** (-0.017886)	-0.065353*** (-0.017886)
Large – Small	-0.004702 (-0.030000)	-0.004702 (-0.030000)
R^2	0.006486	0.006486
Expiration Days	2	2
Observations	4,753,776	4,753,776

Notes: This table reports regression coefficients from tests of the favorite-longshot bias for Kalshi 15M Crypto contracts. Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Liquidity-Aware Results

To further strengthen our findings, we re-estimate the baseline regressions across liquidity-based quartiles. Unlike the spread buckets, which are defined using common thresholds across all market categories, liquidity quartiles are constructed using equal-sized samples within each category.

Importantly, spread bucketing is performed in a category-agnostic manner, as spreads are relatively comparable across categories, allowing for well-populated bins. In contrast, measures such as cumulative traded volume and market depth exhibit substantial heterogeneity across categories. To account for these differences and avoid sparsely populated bins, liquidity quartiles are computed separately within each category.

Following this category-specific liquidity segmentation across spread, volume, and depth, the resulting estimates are reported in the following tables:

1. Spread-Based Results

- (a) Polymarket (15M Crypto): Table 3.6
- (b) Polymarket (NBA): Table 3.7
- (c) Polymarket (Mention Markets): Table 3.8
- (d) Kalshi (15M Crypto): Table 3.9

2. Volume-Based Results

- (a) Polymarket (15M Crypto): Table D.2
- (b) Polymarket (NBA): Table D.3
- (c) Polymarket (Mention Markets): Table D.4
- (d) Kalshi (15M Crypto): Table D.5

3. Depth-Based Results

- (a) Polymarket (15M Crypto): Table D.6
- (b) Polymarket (NBA): Table D.7
- (c) Polymarket (Mention Markets): Table D.8
- (d) Kalshi (15M Crypto): Table D.9

For brevity, we present the spread-based results in the main text, disaggregated by market category (15M Crypto, NBA, and Mention Markets). The corresponding volume- and depth-based specifications are reported in Appendix D.

In addition, we present aggregate plots combining all market categories for each platform in Figures 3.4 and 3.5. The corresponding category-specific plots for spread-, volume-, and depth-based specifications are provided in Appendix D (Figures D.3, D.4, D.5, and D.6).

Figure 3.4: Effect of liquidity on favorite-longshot bias across quartiles for Polymarket.

Figure 3.5: Effect of liquidity on favorite-longshot bias across quartiles for Kalshi.

Table 3.6: Polymarket Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles:

15M Crypto Markets (Spread)

	$\leq 1\%$	1–3%	3–5%	$> 5\%$
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	0.000942 (0.021843)	0.013901 (0.031230)	0.006233 (0.035631)	-0.021933 (0.039190)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	0.010646 (0.031678)	0.004357 (0.031508)	-0.038112 (0.035028)	-0.075992* (0.043106)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	0.000440 (0.024528)	-0.037329 (0.026284)	-0.048907 (0.042869)	0.013457 (0.076213)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	-0.000169 (0.032279)	-0.016893 (0.036730)	-0.021758 (0.043562)	-0.085235 (0.069747)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	0.021389 (0.014131)	0.006770 (0.024960)	-0.005066 (0.037811)	-0.073092 (0.081234)
Small Probabilities	0.005794 (0.024219)	0.009129 (0.028492)	-0.015940 (0.030344)	-0.048962 (0.033466)
Large Probabilities	0.007220 (0.020251)	-0.015817 (0.026147)	-0.025244 (0.035592)	-0.048290 (0.062708)
Large – Small	0.001427 (0.026048)	-0.024946 (0.032443)	-0.009304 (0.035148)	0.000672 (0.058188)
R^2	0.000295	0.002052	0.001846	0.009504
Observations	1,252,854	309,214	32,913	9,887

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table 3.7: Polymarket Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles:

	NBA Markets (Spread)			
	$\leq 1\%$	1–3%	3–5%	$> 5\%$
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	-0.060030** (0.026237)	-0.023012 (0.037114)	-0.063409** (0.027884)	-0.017395 (0.050526)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	0.048095 (0.084409)	0.012335 (0.067079)	-0.062142 (0.064500)	-0.045767 (0.055836)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	0.026418 (0.055671)	0.005999 (0.036113)	-0.025704 (0.033849)	-0.035507 (0.036671)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	0.069620 (0.061252)	0.065200 (0.049487)	0.007619 (0.049143)	-0.032848 (0.055052)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	0.059731 (0.038695)	0.044281 (0.042306)	0.025938 (0.040843)	0.055974* (0.028902)
Small Probabilities	-0.005968 (0.050591)	-0.005339 (0.045907)	-0.062775 (0.040760)	-0.031581 (0.045674)
Large Probabilities	0.051923 (0.036888)	0.038493 (0.032554)	0.002618 (0.028942)	-0.004127 (0.027061)
Large – Small	0.057891 (0.067851)	0.043832 (0.058913)	0.065393 (0.047309)	0.027454 (0.045920)
R^2	0.007688	0.002958	0.003834	0.002467
Observations	441,588	164,028	19,984	10,299

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table 3.8: Polymarket Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles:

	Mention Markets (Spread)			
	$\leq 1\%$	1–3%	3–5%	$> 5\%$
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	-0.004014 (0.010727)	-0.023652*** (0.002766)	-0.037067*** (0.004943)	-0.051277*** (0.001949)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	0.610000*** (0.000000)	-0.365000*** (0.000000)	-0.357000*** (0.000889)	-0.348261*** (0.003447)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	-0.413571*** (0.059936)	-0.411739*** (0.054627)	-0.122500 (0.191145)	0.136667 (0.294840)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	0.082500*** (0.031190)	0.210313*** (0.024718)	0.128182 (0.124492)	-0.085714 (0.139741)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	0.035625 (0.030082)	0.087411** (0.034093)	0.073000*** (0.028086)	0.067895*** (0.022460)
Small Probabilities	0.302993*** (0.005363)	-0.194326*** (0.001383)	-0.197034*** (0.002292)	-0.199769*** (0.001582)
Large Probabilities	-0.098482*** (0.020165)	-0.038005** (0.018573)	0.026227 (0.088355)	0.039616 (0.122117)
Large – Small	-0.401475*** (0.020817)	0.156321*** (0.018765)	0.223261** (0.087851)	0.239385** (0.121991)
R^2	0.251497	0.386553	0.169639	0.258663
Observations	678	472	291	285

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table 3.9: Kalshi Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles:

15M Crypto (Spread)

	$\leq 1\%$	1-3%	3-5%	$> 5\%$
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	-0.035994 (0.025958)	-0.027477 (0.042186)	-0.003576 (0.047704)	-0.086211*** (0.000308)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	-0.097480** (0.042325)	-0.088349 (0.070391)	-0.065988 (0.117308)	-0.063209*** (0.017990)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	-0.111060*** (0.033372)	-0.117251*** (0.036756)	-0.075837 (0.084553)	0.140144*** (0.018527)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	-0.085884*** (0.011364)	-0.079059*** (0.011511)	-0.061243* (0.032016)	-0.020773*** (0.003193)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	0.000309** (0.000141)	-0.023578*** (0.000255)	-0.013730*** (0.001137)	0.089632*** (0.001215)
Small Probabilities	-0.066737* (0.034142)	-0.057913 (0.056289)	-0.034782 (0.082506)	-0.074710*** (0.008841)
Large Probabilities	-0.065545*** (0.014865)	-0.073296*** (0.016004)	-0.050270 (0.038477)	0.069668*** (0.006835)
Large – Small	0.001192 (0.019277)	-0.015383 (0.040284)	-0.015488 (0.044028)	0.144378*** (0.002006)
R^2	0.009789	0.006111	0.001964	0.056755
Expiration Days	2	2	2	2
Observations	2,004,515	2,287,620	417,019	44,622

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

3.3 Looking at Bias With More Nuance

While aggregate measures provide a helpful, high-level view of market efficiency, they often obscure the underlying mechanics of mispricing. To truly understand the structural drivers of the favorite-longshot bias, we must explore higher order dimensions of the data. Evaluating bias purely as a global average fails to capture the dynamic nature of trading. Therefore, we must not only study how bias manifests across different categories of markets, but also, how it evolves with respect to more granular implied probability (price) and the normalized lifecycle of a contract (time). To pinpoint exactly where during a market lifecycle inefficiencies pool, we must evolve our definition of bias.

How Does Bias Differ By Market?

Methodology

To evaluate baseline inefficiencies across different market categories, we apply the following steps:

- **Transaction-Level Market Bias:** We define bias as the difference between the realized outcome and the implied probability (price) at the time of execution. Because real-world prediction markets employ a variety of mutually exclusive outcome pairs—such as ‘Up/Down’ for 15M Crypto Markets, ‘Team A/Team B’ for NBA moneylines, or traditional ‘Yes/No’ structures for Mention Markets and point spreads—we strictly standardize the payoff space. For any binary market, we structurally designate one specific side of the contract as the focal outcome. Formally, for a given market m and trade i , let $O_{m(i)} \in \{0, 1\}$ denote the realized resolution of this focal outcome (where 1 indicates the specific condition was met and 0 indicates it was not), and let $P_i \in [0, 1]$ represent its execution price. The directional bias diagnostic is calculated as:

$$bias_i = O_{m(i)} - P_i$$

- **Cluster-Robust Standard Errors:** To evaluate this bias across categories, we compute the aggregated group mean of $bias_i$. Crucially, trades within the same market share the identical outcome realization and are subject to correlated microstructure shocks. Assuming trade-level bias is independent would artificially deflate standard errors. Therefore, we estimate the group means directly and apply a cluster-robust sandwich covariance estimator grouped at the market level. This ensures our confidence intervals accurately reflect true, market-level uncertainty.

Note: we only use Polymarket data going forward as Kalshi trade data is anonymous and does not provide wallet addresses. Furthermore, Kalshi trade data is one sided and the direction of a trade cannot be inferred as discussed in Appendix B.

Results and Analysis

Figure 3.6 illustrates the aggregated mean bias across three distinct Polymarket market categories: 15M Crypto Markets, Mention Markets, and NBA Markets. The data reveals

Figure 3.6: Aggregated mean bias ($O - P$) grouped by Polymarket market categories. Error bars denote 95% confidence intervals computed via market-clustered robust covariance.

significant heterogeneity in pricing efficiency, demonstrating that the underlying subject matter and structure of the market deeply influence aggregate bias.

The 15M Crypto Markets exhibit a mean bias that is virtually zero. This suggests that these short-duration, high-turnover contracts are highly efficient on average, with implied probabilities closely matching realized frequencies. This pattern may reflect the possibility that traders in financial contracts are, on average, more informed or financially sophisticated than participants in other types of markets.

In contrast, Mention Markets display a notable negative mean bias of approximately -0.04 . Because bias is defined as the realized outcome minus the price, a systematic negative bias indicates that the market broadly overprices these contracts (i.e., P_i remains systematically higher than $O_{m(i)}$). This is consistent with an environment where traders structurally overvalue the likelihood of a specific keyword or narrative trigger occurring.

Conversely, the NBA Markets demonstrate a positive mean bias of roughly $+0.025$. This positive variance suggests a systematic underpricing of the realized outcomes within this sports betting context, pointing to a different set of behavioral or liquidity-driven inefficiencies compared to narrative-driven political or cultural markets.

How Does Bias Differ Through Prices?

Methodology

Historically, researchers have evaluated market bias using “quantile binning”—aggregating prices into arbitrary discrete intervals (e.g., 0% to 20%, 20% to 40%, etc.) and calculating the mean return within each bucket. While computationally straightforward, this approach artificially imposes a step-function on continuous trading data. It mechanically assumes that a trade executed at a 21% implied probability exhibits the identical structural bias as a

trade at 39%, while differing entirely from a trade at 19%. This imposes rigid, discontinuous boundaries and discards the high-frequency granularity inherent to modern prediction market platforms. Crucially, this aggregation averages out underlying microstructure behaviors and ignores distributional differences within each bucket, a distortion that scales proportionately with the size of the bin. For example, collapsing prices into a broad 0.0 to 0.20 interval mathematically neutralizes and entirely obscures the highly idiosyncratic liquidity dynamics that govern extreme longshots in the 0.0 to 0.05 range.

To evaluate the continuous relationship between bias and price, we replace discrete binning with a flexible regression architecture, ensuring statistical robustness through the following steps:

- **Continuous Spline Regression:** To map bias smoothly across the entire probability spectrum (0 to 1) without forcing a rigid linear or preconceived S-shaped relationship, we employ a penalized spline regression framework. Rather than treating implied probability (price) and normalized time as simple linear predictors, our core model incorporates them as continuous regime control variables to isolate their respective marginal effects on bias:

$$bias \sim s(price) + s(time)$$

Here, $s(price)$ and $s(time)$ represent additive smooth blocks constructed using **Penalized Cubic B-Splines** ($degree = 3$).

- **Regularization and GCV Tuning:** To ensure stability and prevent the highly flexible splines from overfitting to idiosyncratic market noise, a smoothing penalty (λ) is applied. This penalty is dynamically tuned using **Generalized Cross-Validation (GCV)** evaluated over a log-spaced grid.
- **Cluster-Robust Inference:** As established in our baseline market analysis, individual trades within the same prediction market are fundamentally correlated, which violates the standard independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) assumption. To prevent mathematically overconfident error margins in our continuous model, we apply the previously defined **Cluster-Robust Sandwich Covariance Estimator**. However, rather than applying it to static group averages, we utilize it here to compute pointwise 95% confidence intervals across the entire fitted spline curve. This ensures that the continuous error bands accurately reflect true market-level uncertainty across the probability spectrum.
- **Quantile-Binning Check:** Because penalized splines possess the mathematical flexibility to potentially “hallucinate” non-linear shapes that are merely artifacts of the spline formulation, we require a non-parametric sanity check. We run a fixed quantile-binning model in parallel with our primary regression. While this binning estimator is too blocky and statistically inefficient to serve as the headline model, it remains mathematically rigid. If our smoothed spline curve successfully tracks the raw, un-smoothed averages of these quantile bins, it provides definitive validation that the observed pricing inefficiencies are genuine market behaviors rather than modeling illusions.

Results and Analysis

By isolating bias as a continuous function of price, Figure 3.7 reveals severe microstructural dynamics that were completely obscured by the aggregate market means.

In the **15M Crypto Markets** (Figure 3.7a), the aggregate mean of zero (observed in the previous section) is revealed to be an illusion created by two offsetting inefficiencies. We observe a pronounced positive bias peaking around the 0.3 price level, and a severe negative bias peaking near the 0.8 level. Strikingly, this is the exact *reverse* of the traditional favorite-longshot bias. Here, the market systematically *underprices* the longshots (0.2 to 0.4) and heavily *overprices* the favorites (0.5 to 1.0), possibly due to the market systematically underestimating the volatility of the underlying cryptocurrency. This pattern is consistent with what we see using our more crude methodology in Figure 3.2.

The **Mention Markets** (Figure 3.7b) display a vastly different behavioral regime. The bias curve remains negative—fluctuating roughly between 0 and -0.1 —across almost the entire probability spectrum. Because $bias = O - P$, a universal negative bias indicates that traders are systematically overpaying for “Yes” contracts regardless of the underlying probability. This aligns with existing literature on “Yes bias” or optimism bias [1], suggesting that in culturally focused markets, participants are structurally prone to overestimating the occurrence of the focal event.

Crucially, this continuous finding directly contrasts with our preliminary, liquidity-agnostic analysis (Table 3.4), which originally suggested the presence of a classic favorite-longshot bias in Mention Markets. That earlier univariate model, which relied on discrete probability bins, indicated severe overpricing at the lower bound and underpricing at the upper bound. By deploying a multivariate penalized spline model ($bias \sim s(price) + s(time)$), we successfully control for normalized time. The resulting $s(price)$ curve isolates the true marginal effect of implied probability by holding time at its average basis.

In prediction markets, price and time are inherently intertwined, but Mention Markets possess a uniquely bimodal liquidity distribution. Prices rarely drift smoothly; rather, they tend to “gap” from extreme longshots to extreme favorites the moment a trigger word is spoken during a live event. Consequently, we hypothesize almost all trading volume in the top probability bin ($0.80 \leq P < 1.00$) generally occurs at the very end of the contract’s lifecycle ($time_pct \approx 1.0$) when the outcome is essentially decided. This is evidenced in Appendix D.2b, which shows that trading volume in Mention Markets experience a sharp spike towards the last 10% of Mention Market market lifecycles.

As we will explore in detail in the subsequent temporal analysis, the timeline of a Mention Market experiences massive volatility and sharp negative bias dips near $t = 0.9$, exactly when live-event trading and intense narrative beliefs flood the market. The positive returns observed in the top bins of the older model could be heavily skewed by these late-stage temporal dynamics and sudden shifts in certainty, rather than pure price-based mispricing. Although, this requires further work to confirm.

Finally, the **NBA Markets** (Figure 3.7c) present a much noisier, yet highly structural pricing curve. At the extreme tails—tail longshots (0.0 to 0.2) and tail favorites (0.8 to 1.0)—we

3.3. LOOKING AT BIAS WITH MORE NUANCE

(a) 15M Crypto Markets

(b) Mention Markets

(c) NBA Markets

Figure 3.7: Conditional bias ($O - P$) as a function of implied probability (price). The solid line represents the penalized cubic B-spline fit, with shaded regions denoting 95% market-clustered confidence intervals. Overlaid points represent the quantile-binning robustness check.

observe a slight negative bias, indicating that extreme certainties are slightly overpriced. However, the center of the distribution exhibits a distinct positive bias (underpricing), which sharply collapses to zero right at the 0.5 mark. This suggests an interesting dynamic: when sports bettors perceive a game as a true coin-flip (evenly matched), the market prices the event with near-perfect efficiency. However, as the probability shifts into the mid-tier ranges, the market struggles to accurately integrate information, resulting in structural underpricing before swinging back to overpricing at the extremes. Again, this matches with Figure 3.2.

Methodology

To fully contextualize pricing inefficiencies like the favorite-longshot bias, we must observe how market efficiency evolves over the lifespan of a contract. Prediction markets inherently operate on strict timelines, bounded by the moment a contract is minted and the moment the real-world reference event resolves. However, because the absolute duration of these markets varies drastically—ranging from 15 minutes for crypto markets to several months for NBA championships—raw timestamps are structurally incomparable.

To evaluate temporal dynamics consistently across all datasets, we implement the following steps:

- **Temporal Normalization:** To establish a universal temporal baseline, we normalize the lifespan of every contract into a standardized, continuous interval from inception ($t = 0$) to expiration ($t = 1$). For any given trade executed at absolute time t , the normalized time percentage is calculated as:

$$\text{time_pct} = \frac{t - t_{\text{market start}}}{t_{\text{market end}} - t_{\text{market start}}}$$

This mathematical translation allows us to directly compare the “early-stage” and “late-stage” behaviors of entirely different asset classes on the exact same scale.

- **Marginal Temporal Evaluation:** Using this standardized axis, we generate conditional curves to evaluate bias against time. We utilize our previously established **Continuous Spline Regression** framework ($\text{bias} \sim s(\text{price}) + s(\text{time})$).
- **Robustness and Boundary Diagnostics:** To validate the shape of our temporal curves, we continue to apply both **Cluster-Robust Inference** and the **Quantile-Binning Check**. Furthermore, because trading volume in prediction markets often exhibits extreme chronological clustering—with liquidity highly concentrated at market open and immediately before expiration—interpretations near the extreme boundaries ($t = 0$ and $t = 1$) require careful evaluation of data support. Diagnostics confirming sufficient absolute trade counts across the temporal timeline are provided in Appendix D.2.

Results and Analysis

The temporal analysis in Figure 3.8 demonstrates that prediction markets do not experience a uniform, linear march toward efficiency. Instead, bias fluctuates dynamically as new

3.3. LOOKING AT BIAS WITH MORE NUANCE

(a) 15M Crypto Markets

(b) Mention Markets

(c) NBA Markets

Figure 3.8: Conditional bias ($O - P$) as a function of normalized time from inception ($t = 0$) to expiration ($t = 1$). The solid line represents the penalized cubic B-spline fit, with shaded regions denoting 95% market-clustered confidence intervals. Overlaid points represent the quantile-binning robustness check.

information environments and trader behaviors emerge over a contract’s lifecycle.

This suggests that early in the contract’s lifecycle, traders systematically overestimate the underlying cryptocurrency’s volatility, paying a premium for the possibility of a favorable price swing while there is still time on the clock. Essentially, participants over-extrapolate the potential for large, directional market movements, leading them to overprice the contract ($P > O$).

However, as the expiration window drastically narrows (post $t = 0.8$), this behavioral tendency flips. The emergence of a positive bias indicates that participants begin to systematically *underprice* the realized outcomes ($P < O$). In the context of hyper-short 15-minute windows, this likely reflects a failure to accurately price in late-stage variance or “micro-volatility.” As the clock runs out, traders may anchor too heavily to the current spot price, underestimating the probability of a last-second tick pushing the contract into the money. Together, this curve illustrates a market that transitions from pricing in too much hope and variance at the start, to an under-reaction to immediate, short-term volatility at the very end.

In the **15M Crypto Markets** (Figure 3.8a), the market opens with a notable negative bias of approximately -0.1 at $t = 0$, remaining relatively stable through the first half of the lifecycle. However, near $t = 0.6$, the bias spikes upward, transitioning into a positive regime between $t = 0.8$ and $t = 1$. As the market nears completion, the 95% confidence intervals systematically contract, reflecting increased certainty and tighter pricing as the final crypto price action solidifies. This suggests that early in the contract’s lifecycle, traders systematically overestimate the underlying cryptocurrency’s volatility, paying a premium for the possibility of a favorable price swing while there is still time on the clock. Participants over-extrapolate the potential for large, directional market movements, leading them to overprice the contract. However, as the expiration window drastically narrows (post $t = 0.8$), this behavioral tendency flips. The emergence of a positive bias indicates that participants begin to systematically underprice the realized outcomes. In the context of short 15-minute windows, this likely reflects a failure to accurately price in late-stage variance. As the clock runs out, traders may anchor too heavily to the current spot price, underestimating the probability of a last-second tick pushing the contract into the money.

The **Mention Markets** (Figure 3.8b) exhibit a much more volatile progression, accompanied by substantial contraction in the confidence interval as the resolution approaches. The market opens with negative bias, but experiences sharp spikes toward zero near $t = 0.2$ and $t = 0.4$. While these spikes could reflect early information revelation, their clustering may also be artifacts of noise in lower-liquidity early trading. After $t = 0.6$, the bias remains much lower—hovering near zero or turning slightly positive—before dipping sharply negative again around $t = 0.9$. This late-stage negative dip is particularly revealing; it likely coincides with the actual occurrence of the referenced event (e.g., a political speech), where intense trader interest and strong narrative beliefs flood the market (supported by the sharp increase in trading activity seen in Appendix D.2b), temporarily creating more bias before the final, rapid convergence to zero at $t = 1$.

Finally, the **NBA Markets** (Figure 3.8c) show a slight narrowing of the confidence inter-

val over time, but the curve’s smoothness is highly bifurcated. During the first 75% of the normalized timeline—which largely corresponds to the pre-game period where fundamental expectations are locked in and trading interest is relatively calm—the curve is remarkably smooth, generally exhibiting a structural positive bias (underpricing). Furthermore, the relatively constrained magnitude of mispricing here compared to our other datasets may stem from the symmetric nature of the underlying propositions. Unlike Mention Markets (“Yes/No”) or Cryptocurrency contracts (“Up/Down”), which frequently suffer from structural default biases or directional momentum expectations, sports matchups (Team A versus Team B) generally lack a universal, implicit psychological bias favoring one abstract side over the other. However, the final 25% of the timeline becomes significantly noisier. This increased volatility perfectly maps to live, in-game trading, where momentum shifts and rapid point swings cause the bias to momentarily dip negative near $t = 0.75$ before ultimately resolving.

3.4 Transitioning From Bias to Edge

Up to this point, our analysis has focused exclusively on market-wide *bias*, defined as the raw difference between the realized outcome and the implied probability ($bias = O - P$). Bias serves as a diagnostic tool for structural market inefficiency—it tells us when the market, as an aggregate pricing mechanism, is systematically wrong. However, bias alone cannot answer the fundamental microstructural questions: *who* is creating this mispricing, and *who* is profiting from it?

To answer these questions, we must transition our analytical framework from market-wide bias to individual edge. *Edge* measures the directional expected value—or profitability—of a specific trade. Because participants can choose to buy or sell a contract, edge incorporates the participant’s directional stance. Formally, for a given trade i , we define a directional indicator $d_i \in \{+1, -1\}$, where $+1$ represents buying the “Yes” contract and -1 represents selling it (or buying “No”). The individual edge is thus calculated as:

$$edge_i = d_i \times (O_{m(i)} - P_i)$$

Notice that for a ‘Buy’ trade, $edge = O - P$ (identical to bias). However, for a ‘Sell’ trade, the edge is inverted to $P - O$. By shifting our target variable to edge, we transition from observing static mispricing to evaluating participant skill and profitability. Furthermore, because every executed trade involves a Maker (resting liquidity) and a Taker (aggressive liquidity), their directional edges are mechanically inverse to one another before fees, where $edge_{maker} \approx -edge_{taker}$. To evaluate whether aggressive trading behavior is driven by informed signals or uninformed noise, we isolate the “Taker” side of the order book. Takers pay the spread to demand immediate execution; measuring their edge reveals whether they are successfully trading on unpriced information or simply bleeding expected value to passive market makers.

How Does Edge Differ Through Prices?

By plotting Taker edge against execution prices, we can observe whether participants demanding liquidity at specific probability tiers possess genuine alpha, or if they are systematically overpaying for immediacy.

Methodology

To construct our Taker edge curves and isolate aggressive liquidity demands across the probability spectrum, we implement the following steps:

- **Directional Role Expansion:** To maximize the utility of our data, we do not simply filter our dataset down to taker-initiated rows. Instead, we employ a role expansion technique where each cleaned trade is duplicated into one maker row and one taker row. By flipping the directional indicator (d_i) and extracting the inverse contract perspective, we successfully mathematically reconstruct what the taker would have paid even from maker-tagged data.
- **Market Fixed Effects (Within-Market Demeaning):** A critical methodological shift in evaluating individual edge is the introduction of a Market Fixed Effect (α_m). In our initial bias models, we intentionally evaluated raw data to preserve natural cross-market payoff variations. However, because we are now analyzing participant-level performance across a highly diverse set of contracts, we must systematically control for the baseline difficulty and structural idiosyncrasies of each specific market. To achieve this computationally, we calculate the market-specific mean for our target variable and all regime basis functions, denoted as $\bar{X}_m = \frac{1}{N_m} \sum_{i=1}^{N_m} X_{im}$. We then transform the data by subtracting this mean from each individual observation:

$$\tilde{X}_{im} = X_{im} - \bar{X}_m$$

This mathematical transformation strictly isolates within-market variation by perfectly differencing out the market-specific constant ($\alpha_m - \alpha_m = 0$). Consequently, this ensures that our estimates reflect actual predictive skill relative to the market's specific pricing baseline, rather than being disproportionately skewed by the ultimate binary 1 or 0 resolution of the underlying event.

- **Pooled Role Regression:** We evolve our **Continuous Spline Regression** architecture to model both maker and taker dynamics simultaneously. We achieve this by interacting the role indicator (is_taker) with our continuous regime blocks on the demeaned data:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{edge}_{im} = & \widetilde{is_taker}_{im} + s(\widetilde{time}_{im}) + is_taker \times \widetilde{s(time)}_{im} + is_taker \times \widetilde{s(price)}_{im} \\ & + s(\widetilde{price}_{im}) + \tilde{\epsilon}_{im} \end{aligned}$$

To isolate the specific taker curve, we generate conditional fitted predictions from this model by evaluating the function at $is_taker = 1$.

- **Platform Exclusions and Robustness:** Due to the necessity of reconstructing precise maker/taker execution roles and directional stances, platforms without sufficient trade-level microstructure granularity (such as Kalshi) are explicitly excluded from these edge-based regressions. Finally, we ensure the stability and validity of our estimates by continuing to apply **Generalized Cross-Validation (GCV)** for smoothing penalty tuning, **Cluster-Robust Inference** for our standard errors. We drop the **Adaptive Quantile-Binning Check** for visual clarity going forward.

Results and Analysis

The evaluation of Taker edge provides a stark contrast to our aggregate bias curves. Across our datasets, we observe a generally positive taker edge. Because aggressive takers must cross the bid-ask spread to execute, a positive pre-fee edge indicates adverse selection against market makers; takers possess enough directional momentum or informational advantage to systematically overcome the baseline cost of liquidity.

In the **15M Crypto Markets** (Figure 3.9a), the taker edge is positive across the probability spectrum, though the overall magnitudes are extremely small. The curve forms a slight U-shape, with the taker edge compressing to approximately zero near the center (0.4 to 0.6). This indicates that at the point of maximum uncertainty (the 0.5 coin-flip), any informational advantage takers have is perfectly offset by the spread. At the extreme probability wings, however, the edge drifts positively, possibly reflecting latency arbitrage or more informed traders.

The **Mention Markets** (Figure 3.9b) present a distinct structural divergence. While the taker edge remains entirely positive, it exhibits pronounced peaks around the 0.2 and 0.9 price levels, coupled with a similar U-shaped dip around 0.5. Most notably, the edge sharply collapses toward zero at the extreme 0.0 and 1.0 tails—a phenomenon not observed in the 15M Crypto or NBA Markets. This pattern is highly characteristic of live information integration. The peak at 0.2 likely captures aggressive takers buying into an emerging narrative exactly as an event begins, while the peak at 0.9 reflects late-stage traders rushing to lock in certainty right before the market officially resolves. The collapse at the absolute tails reflects that once information is entirely ubiquitous and certainty is absolute, the informational alpha of demanding liquidity vanishes.

In the **NBA Markets** (Figure 3.9c), the taker edge is positive throughout and structurally flat, exhibiting only a very slight U-shape. The numerical value of the edge is small across the entire curve. Sports bettors demanding liquidity possess a slight pre-fee mathematical edge, but it is likely entirely gone once actual trading fees are applied.

How Does Edge Differ Through Time?

Having established how aggressive liquidity demand interacts with implied probability, we must sequentially evaluate how this dynamic evolves over the contract’s normalized lifecycle. By plotting Taker edge against normalized time ($t = 0$ to $t = 1$), we can isolate whether the informational advantage of takers is concentrated at market inception, during live-event integration, or in the final moments before expiration.

(a) 15M Crypto Markets

(b) Mention Markets

(c) NBA Markets

Figure 3.9: Conditional Taker Edge as a function of implied probability (price). The solid line represents the penalized cubic B-spline fit, with shaded regions denoting 95% market-clustered confidence intervals. check.

Methodology

To evaluate the temporal dimension of Taker edge, we build upon the participant-level framework established in the previous section by shifting our focal axis:

- **Marginal Temporal Evaluation:** We utilize the exact **Pooled Role Regression** established previously, which models both maker and taker dynamics simultaneously across our continuous regime blocks:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{edge}_{im} = & \widetilde{is_taker}_{im} + s(\widetilde{time}_{im}) + \widetilde{is_taker} \times s(\widetilde{time})_{im} + \widetilde{is_taker} \times s(\widetilde{price})_{im} \\ & + s(\widetilde{price}_{im}) + \tilde{\epsilon}_{im} \end{aligned}$$

- **Conditional Taker Predictions:** To isolate the pure temporal effect, we generate conditional fitted predictions specifically for aggressive takers ($is_taker = 1$) evaluated across the **Temporal Normalization** grid ($t = 0$ to $t = 1$). To ensure we are measuring the strict marginal effect of time rather than confounding price dynamics, the non-focal continuous variable ($price$) is held mathematically constant by setting its spline block to the sample-average basis value.
- **Consistent Inference:** As with our price-based edge analysis, this model natively relies on **Market Fixed Effects (Within-Market Demeaning)** to absorb baseline structural differences and outcome variances across different contracts. Finally, the pointwise 95% confidence intervals are computed using **Cluster-Robust Inference** to properly account for within-market trade dependence.

Results and Analysis

The temporal curves in Figure 3.10 demonstrate that the magnitude and persistence of a taker’s edge are heavily dictated by the market’s specific information environment.

In the **15M Crypto Markets** (Figure 3.10a), the taker edge curve is flat and hovering just above zero. The overall movement in the curve is so minute that it is virtually indistinguishable from statistical noise. This suggests that over an ultra-short 15-minute horizon, the passage of time does not materially alter the expected edge of demanding liquidity. The market is continuously reacting to an external, highly liquid spot market; therefore, takers face a relatively constant (and negligible) pre-fee edge regardless of whether the contract is in its first or final minute.

The **Mention Markets** (Figure 3.10b) present a much more structural temporal dynamic. The taker edge remains firmly positive throughout the vast majority of the contract’s lifecycle. Because Mention Markets often revolve around unpredictable, exogenous triggers (e.g. a spoken phrase), takers who aggressively cross the spread based on live information possess genuine, unpriced edge against resting limit orders. However, as the market approaches absolute completion ($t \approx 1.0$), we observe a noticeable downward dip. As the underlying event concludes and information becomes entirely ubiquitous, the latency advantage evaporates. Passive makers can confidently price the known outcome, instantly wiping out the edge of demanding liquidity.

(a) 15M Crypto Markets

(b) Mention Markets

(c) NBA Markets

Figure 3.10: Conditional Taker Edge as a function of normalized time from inception ($t = 0$) to expiration ($t = 1$). The solid line represents the penalized cubic B-spline fit, with shaded regions denoting 95% market-clustered confidence intervals. Overlaid points represent the fixed quantile-binning robustness check. 40

In the **NBA Markets** (Figure 3.10c), we observe a strictly positive, taker edge throughout the event lifecycle. The curve exhibits subtle structural undulations: it starts slightly higher at $t = 0$ (reflecting early-informed takers betting against stale pre-game lines), dips toward its lowest point near $t = 0.4$, and then rises to a “mini-peak” around $t = 0.8$. This late-stage peak likely reflects live-game momentum trading, where takers aggressively price live during the game before makers can adjust their spreads. Finally, consistent with the Mention Markets, the edge collapses lower as the game reaches its final seconds at $t = 1.0$ and certainty takes over. While these structural shifts are identifiable, the total vertical movement of the curve remains incredibly minimal.

How Does Edge Differ By Participant Size?

Having established how directional edge fluctuates across execution prices and time, we now turn to the demographic composition of the participants. A central question in market microstructure is whether informational alpha is concentrated among highly capitalized, sophisticated actors (Whales) or if smaller participants are capable of extracting edge. By mapping continuous participant size against trade profitability, we can empirically test whether capital dominance correlates meaningfully with predictive skill.

Methodology

To empirically test how edge scales with capital allocation without introducing look-ahead bias, we map continuous participant size against trade profitability using the following framework:

- **Dynamic Participant Sizing:** To construct a continuous metric of relative participant size, denoted as *participant_size_pct* $\in [0, 1]$, we implement a chronological play-by-play ledger that reconstructs the complete trading history and net positions of thousands of individual proxy wallets after every execution. Rather than statically assigning a size label based on a trader’s total position at the end of the market’s lifecycle (which would introduce severe future-data leakage), this metric is calculated using a continuously growing time window. At the precise moment of execution, a participant’s cumulative position is ranked dynamically against the cumulative position of all active participants in that market up to that exact timestamp.
- **Whale Categorization:** This dynamic approach generates a real-time, cross-sectional ranking, placing the participant into a continuous percentile distribution based strictly on information available at the time of the trade. For categorical contrast analysis, participants executing trades while ranked in the top decile of this growing window (≥ 0.90) are classified as Whales.
- **Size-Integrated Spline Regression:** We incorporate this dynamic participant size into our established **Continuous Spline Regression** framework by adding it as a third continuous smooth block alongside our standard regime controls:

$$edge \sim s(participant_size_pct) + s(price) + s(time) + \text{Market FE}$$

This model natively retains our **Market Fixed Effects (Within-Market Demeaning)** to absorb baseline structural cross-market differences.

- **Marginal Sizing Evaluation:** To isolate the specific effect of capital size and generate our headline curves, we compute the conditional fitted edge prediction evaluated across a grid of participant size percentiles. To prevent the varying price or time regimes from skewing the results, the non-focal variables (*price* and *time*) are held constant at their sample-average basis values. Finally, point-wise 95% confidence intervals are generated using **Cluster-Robust Inference** to maintain consistent error accounting.

Results and Analysis

The relationship between participant size and trading edge (Figure 3.11) defies traditional financial intuition, which typically assumes that the largest, most capitalized participants possess the greatest informational advantage. Instead, we observe a consistent decay in edge as participant size increases across multiple market types.

In the **15M Crypto Markets** (Figure 3.11a), the highest directional edge is actually concentrated at the absolute bottom of the size distribution, specifically near the 10th percentile (0.1). From this peak, the edge decays steadily as participant size increases. The heavily capitalized Whales (those commanding the largest position shares) exhibit the lowest relative edge in the market. It is worth noting a structural anomaly in this specific projection: the entire spline curve remains in positive territory. Because prediction markets are closed systems (a zero-sum environment before fees, where one participant’s positive edge must be funded by another’s negative edge), a globally positive curve in this specific conditional slice suggests the presence of residual statistical noise or an artifact of evaluating the marginal curve at the specific sample-average basis of the regime controls. Nonetheless, the monotonic *decay* in relative performance from small-order traders to Whales remains a strong structural signal.

This inverse relationship is far more pronounced in the **Mention Markets** (Figure 3.11b), where the lower half of the participant distribution (< 0.5 percentile) maintains a positive expected edge, while profitability collapses sharply for the largest Whales. This dynamic likely stems from the specific demographics of Mention Markets. Unlike traditional financial markets where capital dominance correlates with institutional sophistication, prediction market Whales in cultural or political markets are frequently highly capitalized individuals trading on ideological conviction rather than objective probability. These participants disproportionately drive the structural “Yes Bias” observed earlier in our analysis, willingly overpaying for large positions in their preferred outcomes. Conversely, the smaller participants exhibiting positive edge likely represent sharper, objective traders who capture alpha by systematically providing liquidity to, and fading the narrative biases of, these overconfident, highly capitalized participants.

The **NBA Markets** (Figure 3.11c) exhibit a dampened version of the Mention Market dynamics. The broad middle percentiles is highly noisy but centers tightly around zero edge, reflecting the general efficiency of sports betting lines. However, the extreme upper tail of the distribution once again plunges into negative territory. Even in highly mature

(a) 15M Crypto Markets

(b) Mention Markets

(c) NBA Markets

Figure 3.11: Conditional Edge as a function of continuous participant size percentile. The solid line represents the penalized cubic B-spline fit, with shaded regions denoting 95% market-clustered confidence intervals.

sports markets, the absolute largest participants systematically bleed expected value, likely paying a heavy premium for liquidity or suffering from adverse selection when defending large, passive positions against sharper, smaller betting syndicates.

3.5 Studying the Vocality of Traders

To evaluate whether more vocal traders exhibit any informational edge, we must first establish a rigorous definition of ‘vocality’ within the context of prediction markets. In this setting, comments are rarely just expressions of generalized optimism or pessimism; they are often explicit assertions about the likelihood of an outcome, reactions to real-time market events, or simply insubstantial noise. A trader might post commentary suggesting an event will occur, will not occur, or express fundamental uncertainty. Consequently, the analytical task is not to quantify generic emotional sentiment, but rather to extract a trader’s *directional stance* relative to a specific market’s resolution.

Traditional sentiment classifiers, which measure polarity (positive versus negative tone), are inherently insufficient for this task. For instance, a comment such as “*This is garbage!*” carries strongly negative sentiment but provides zero directional information regarding the contract’s outcome. Conversely, a neutral-toned statement such as “*There is no chance Trump says ‘Biden’ more than 10 times during this speech*” conveys a definitive directional claim without triggering traditional polarity flags. Because prediction markets fundamentally resolve to binary outcomes (e.g., YES or NO), the core NLP task must determine whether a given comment structurally supports or contradicts one of these specific resolutions.

Classifying The Vocality Of Traders With NLP

To operationalize this concept of directional stance, we employ a Natural Language Inference (NLI) framework. NLI is a supervised learning task in which a model receives two sequences of text—a *premise* (p) and a *hypothesis* (h)—and classifies their logical relationship into one of three categories:

- **Entailment:** The hypothesis logically follows from the premise.
- **Contradiction:** The hypothesis is logically inconsistent with the premise.
- **Neutral:** The premise neither entails nor contradicts the hypothesis.

Formally, the model estimates the conditional probability distribution over the class labels $y \in \{\text{Entailment, Contradiction, Neutral}\}$ given the text pairs:

$$P(y | p, h) = \text{Softmax}(\text{Model}(p, h))$$

We reinterpret comment-level stance detection as an exact NLI task by assigning the user’s unstructured comment as the premise ($p = c_i$) and a structured statement describing a potential market resolution as the hypothesis. For each binary market, we construct two symmetric hypotheses:

1. H_{yes} : “The correct resolution is YES. Market: [Description]”

Figure 3.12: Comparison of Bi-Encoder and Cross-Encoder transformer architectures. The cross-encoder allows for full self-attention across both the premise and hypothesis sequences, capturing nuanced logical interaction. Adapted from [26].

2. H_{no} : “The correct resolution is NO. Market: [Description]”

By evaluating whether a comment entails or contradicts each candidate resolution, we transform unstructured sentiment analysis into a conditional reasoning problem. This reframing successfully avoids brittle heuristic keyword matching, instead leveraging a model trained explicitly to reason about semantic implication and logical consistency.

To execute this, we employ the pretrained transformer model `cross-encoder/nli-deberta-v3-base`, fine-tuned on the Stanford Natural Language Inference (SNLI) and Multi-Genre NLI (MNLI) benchmarks.

There are three primary rationales for selecting this specific architecture:

- **SNLI and MNLI Fine-Tuning:** These datasets train models to detect logical entailment and contradiction across highly diverse text genres. Although not inherently domain-specific to financial markets, they provide robust, generalized supervision for conditional reasoning between sentence pairs. Because stance detection in prediction markets is fundamentally a logical inference task, MNLI/SNLI-trained models are structurally aligned perfectly with our objective. Moreover, this fine-tuning data was collected between roughly 2012–2020, while our prediction-market comments are from 2025–2026. As a result, the model cannot have been exposed to the underlying events or outcomes in our sample, eliminating time leakage and ensuring that stance predictions reflect general linguistic reasoning rather than memorized future information.
- **Cross-Encoder Architecture:** We specifically adopt a cross-encoder rather than an embedding-based bi-encoder similarity approach. In a bi-encoder system, the comment and the market description would be embedded independently and compared via a

simple geometric distance metric like cosine similarity. While computationally efficient, bi-encoders lack token-level interaction between the two sentences. By contrast, a cross-encoder jointly processes the concatenated premise and hypothesis pair, allowing full multi-head self-attention across both sequences simultaneously. This interaction is critical and seen in Figure 3.12; it enables the model to accurately capture negations (“will not”), conditional phrasing, and implicit logical structures that independently embedded sentences often miss.

- **DeBERTa-v3 Enhancements:** The underlying DeBERTa-v3 architecture incorporates disentangled attention and enhanced mask decoder training, granting the model an improved ability to capture syntactic and semantic relationships between tokens. In the context of NLI, this enhances sensitivity to subtle logical structures without necessitating domain-specific fine-tuning on our prediction market data.

Aggregating Directional Stance

To translate the model’s probabilistic outputs into a single, continuous metric of directional stance for our regressions, we compute a net alignment score (s_c) for each individual comment. However, prediction market participants often post multiple times prior to executing a trade. To capture a trader’s true accumulated public stance at the precise moment of execution, we calculate the arithmetic mean of all their prior semantic scores.

For a trader who has authored N comments ($N > 0$) prior to a specific trade i , their raw aggregated vocality score is computed. Crucially, because our baseline NLI sentiment scores inherently evaluate conviction toward the focal “Yes” outcome (Outcome A), we must mathematically align this sentiment with the participant’s actual trading behavior. If a participant executes a “Sell” order ($d_i = -1$), their execution is fundamentally aligned with the negative outcome. To ensure our metric universally represents conviction *in the direction of the executed trade*, we multiply the raw average by the trade’s directional indicator. The final, trade-aligned vocality score is defined as:

$$sentiment_avg_i = \max \left(-1, \min \left(1, d_i \times \frac{1}{N} \sum_{c=1}^N s_c \right) \right)$$

This metric, $sentiment_avg_i$, is mathematically clipped to strictly bound it within the interval $[-1, 1]$. In this aligned framework, +1 indicates absolute public conviction in the direction of the executed trade (i.e., highly bullish commentary prior to a “Buy” order, or highly bearish commentary prior to a “Sell” order). Conversely, -1 indicates absolute public conviction *against* their own trade (e.g., bearish commentary followed by a “Buy” order), and 0 indicates either a lack of commentary, purely neutral statements, or perfectly offsetting conflicting statements.

This bounded, structured approach provides an economically interpretable method for translating unstructured community commentary into a quantified, trade-aligned directional stance. It allows us to segment traders by their publicly expressed beliefs, enabling a direct empirical

investigation into whether highly vocal participants generate informational edge or simply contribute to market noise.

Example Output

The following examples (summarized in Table 3.10) illustrate how the NLI-based stance scoring framework maps linguistic intensity and directional conviction into economically meaningful sentiment magnitudes.

Table 3.10: NLI-Based Stance Scoring Examples

Linguistic Category	Example Statement	Score	Framework Interpretation
Strongly Bullish	“UP UP UP – this is the time to buy...”	0.936	High semantic alignment with the positive outcome anchor.
Emphatic Bearish	“DOWN TO THE ABYSS YEEE-HAA”	−0.455	Meaningful alignment with the negative resolution.
Non-Contextual	“get a job”	0.000	No directional stance; lacks semantic entailment with either outcome.

As demonstrated, scores emerge from the relative entailment strength between the comment and competing outcome hypotheses rather than generic sentiment polarity. This ensures that magnitude reflects true directional conviction toward resolution rather than emotional tone alone.

How Does The Edge of Traders Differ Through Their Vocality?

Having established the continuous, trade-aligned directional stance metric (*sentiment_avg*), we must test whether a participant’s public vocality translates into predictive edge. Unlike our previous structural analyses, we intentionally drop the continuous price and time regime controls. This isolates the global average effect of public commentary on expected value, regardless of when or at what probability the trade was executed.

Methodology

To ensure our findings are strictly isolated from baseline market difficulty, we continue to apply **Market Fixed Effects (Within-Market Demeaning)** to all target variables and covariates. Standard errors are computed using **Cluster-Robust Inference** grouped at the market level.

We isolate the subset of traders who provided public commentary (*has_comment* = 1) to evaluate how their stated conviction correlates with informational edge. We intentionally

avoid continuous-time spline modeling for this specific analysis, as the relationship between vocality and edge is noisy.

The relationship is estimated per platform and database using the following specification for **Continuous Sentiment Interaction**:

$$edge_{im} = \beta_1 sentiment_avg_{im} + \alpha_m + \epsilon_{im}$$

In this specification, we utilize only data points with comments and from the taker side. *sentiment_avg* represents the trade-aligned mean of all semantic scores authored by a trader prior to trade i , a value bounded between $[-1, 1]$. The coefficient β_1 captures the linear slope of edge as a trader’s stated conviction magnitude increases.

For visual validation, we rely on scatter plots of realized edge against *sentiment_avg* for all vocal traders.

Results and Analysis

Figure 3.13: Scatter Analysis of Edge vs. Sentiment across various Polymarket categories.

Our NLI-based sentiment analysis and associated scatter plots (3.13) are highly noisy and visually dominated by artifacts that plausibly arise from the sentence-pair NLI methodology itself (e.g., thresholding effects, label uncertainty near decision boundaries, and instability under small wording changes). This methodological noise is further confounded by the

extreme baseline noise already present in edge plots, making it difficult to distinguish genuine signal from measurement error or visualization-driven structure. In practice, the resulting figures were non-interpretable—any apparent patterns were not robust enough to support defensible inference—so we did not proceed with downstream modeling that would treat public vocality as a reliable explanatory variable for trader edge.

Within those constraints, the evidence we do have suggests that public vocality is not currently an informative predictor of trader edge. Stated conviction in these markets appears to be dominated by noise, social signaling, or ideological “cheerleading” rather than reflecting private informational advantages. That said, this conclusion remains preliminary and is best interpreted as “no detectable signal under the present measurement pipeline,” rather than as a definitive null. The visible banding suggests the NLI model effectively “snaps” many observations to a few similarity-driven score clusters, rather than producing a smooth distribution of conviction. This discretization constrains cross-sectional variation and limits our ability to detect a meaningful relationship between sentiment and realized trading edge. Further work using more expressive contextual reasoning (e.g., LLM-based stance/intent extraction, conversational context, irony/sarcasm detection) and/or higher-density datasets (more comments per trader per market, richer metadata, longer observation windows) may yet uncover subtle predictive structure that our current sentence-pair NLI framework cannot reliably resolve.

Chapter 4

Scalable Prediction Market Data Aggregation

4.1 System Architecture

To study pricing bias in the level of detail we desired, we built a custom dataset and data ingestion system. Our high-performance, multi-threaded tracking engine is designed to ingest, normalize, and persist real-time and historical data from prediction markets, specifically Polymarket and Kalshi. The system handles complex asynchronous WebSocket streams, REST-based historical backfilling, and dynamic database batching via a Single-Writer SQLite Multiton pattern.

The system, illustrated in Figure 4.1, is built on a modular, event-driven architecture utilizing Python’s threading for parallel market tracking, `asyncio` for concurrent network I/O within trackers, and a thread-safe queue for data offloading. This design isolates individual market trackers, ensuring that rate limits or network disruptions in one market do not cascade and interrupt data collection in others. Within each thread, asynchronous loops manage simultaneous connections to comments, Level 1 (best bid/ask), Level 2 (full order book depth), and trade execution WebSocket streams.

A core challenge in multi-platform analysis is schema divergence, which is documented in detail in Appendix B. Our engine implements a robust normalization layer that translates disparate API behaviors—such as Kalshi’s continuous delta-based order book updates, which require precise local state reconstruction, versus Polymarket’s distinct snapshot mechanisms—into unified, strongly typed data structures. This standardization is critical for ensuring consistent cross-platform inference on pricing bias.

Finally, the system addresses the fundamental impedance mismatch between high-velocity network reads and synchronous disk writes. It handles complex asynchronous WebSocket streams and REST-based historical backfilling by decoupling ingestion from storage. Data is routed through a thread-safe queue to a dedicated persistence layer employing a Single-Writer SQLite Multiton pattern. To prevent database locking during periods of bursty or irregular

data flow, the writer utilizes Dynamic Exponential Moving Average (EMA) batching, which continuously adjusts write sizes based on real-time ingestion rates to maximize throughput.

Figure 4.1: Expanded System Architecture: Showing orchestration, parallel normalization, interface-based persistence routing, and modular database options.

We explain the architecture and the database schema in more depth in Appendix A and Appendix C.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

This paper set out to deconstruct the assumption that modern prediction markets function as perfectly efficient aggregators of continuous "ground truth". By shifting the analytical lens away from static, end-of-day market averages and toward a granular, play-by-play ledger of individual participant behavior, we have demonstrated that predictive signals are heavily distorted by the structural mechanics of the market, the demographic composition of its participants, and the passage of time.

Crucially, executing this level of granular microstructure analysis necessitated overcoming significant data fragmentation across modern exchanges. To achieve this, we designed and implemented a custom, high-performance data engineering architecture capable of asynchronously ingesting, normalizing, and persisting real-time WebSocket order flow and historical REST data across both Polymarket and Kalshi. By leveraging dynamic Exponential Moving Average (EMA) batching and scalable SQLite persistence patterns, this unified tracking engine abstracts away platform-specific schema divergences. This system not only served as the foundational data layer for the empirical findings in this study, but also establishes a robust, reproducible framework for future cross-platform prediction market research.

Our empirical findings challenge several established assumptions in behavioral finance. Most notably, we demonstrate that the historically documented favorite-longshot bias is, in modern market contexts, not present. When modeled, with control for temporal volatility and bimodal liquidity distributions, using multivariate penalized splines, Mention Markets do not exhibit an S-shaped favorite-longshot bias, but rather a continuous, pervasive "Yes Bias" [1]. This indicates that in cultural or political environments, the implied probability for an event to occur deviates systematically from the realized probability.

Furthermore, we mapped the distribution of informational edge across the participant pool, overturning the assumption that capital size equates to market sophistication. Across our datasets, we observed a consistent decay in expected value as participant portfolio size increased. Rather than acting as sophisticated arbiters of probability, highly capitalized Whales systematically bled edge to small-order traders. This suggests a unique microstructural dynamic in which Whales trade heavily on ideological conviction rather than informational advantage.

Finally, our investigation into trader vocality via Natural Language Inference (NLI) analysis seems to indicate a decoupling between social signal and market performance. We find no statistically significant correlation between sentiment intensity and realized informational edge. This suggests that the "loudest" voices in the market are not synonymous with "smart money," but are instead generating a communicative signal that is independent of predictive accuracy.

Ultimately, this research confirms that while prediction markets are powerful forecasting tools, their signals are inherently noisy. If institutional actors are to reliably extract secondary signals from these platforms, they cannot treat the raw implied probability as absolute truth. They must actively denoise the data by contextualizing it within the contract's lifecycle, adjusting for the baseline liquidity environment, and filtering out belief-driven liquidity shocks generated by heavily capitalized participants exhibiting systematic bias.

5.1 Limitations and Future Work

While this paper establishes a robust framework for wallet-level and temporal analysis, several methodological, analytical, and data-gathering limitations define the boundaries of our current findings and present clear avenues for future research.

Model Limitations

Our analytical framework possesses several structural limitations that warrant consideration:

- **Spline Robustness and Boundary Effects:** First, while penalized cubic B-splines offer significant advantages over discrete quantile binning by capturing continuous, non-linear dynamics, they introduce their own structural vulnerabilities. The mathematical behavior of splines—particularly at the extreme probability tails ($price \approx 0$ or $price \approx 1$) and temporal boundaries ($time \approx 0$ or $time \approx 1$)—can be highly sensitive to data sparsity. Despite our use of Generalized Cross-Validation (GCV) to penalize overfitting, spline curves naturally exhibit wider variance and potential artifacting in these low-support regions. Consequently, interpretations of edge and bias at the absolute margins require caution, as the flexibility of the spline may over-extrapolate noise rather than capture genuine microstructural phenomena.
- **Dimensionality of Regime Smooths:** Relatedly, our baseline models utilize additive regime smooths ($s(price) + s(time)$). While effective for isolating marginal effects without overwhelming the data, this approach inherently assumes independence between price and time dynamics, failing to capture scenarios where the effect of price changes non-linearly over time.
- **Varying Trade and Market Liquidity:** Finally, our methodology aggregates trades across markets that exhibit vastly different liquidity profiles. While our models incorporate **Market Fixed Effects** to absorb baseline outcome variances and employ cluster-robust standard errors, these linear transformations do not fully account for the non-linear impact of liquidity depth on price discovery. A trade executed in a

highly liquid \$10 million political market faces a structurally different bid-ask spread and adverse selection environment than a trade in a sparse, illiquid \$10,000 cultural market. Furthermore, standardizing the temporal axis ($t = 0$ to $t = 1$) across contracts of vastly different absolute durations artificially stretches or compresses liquidity clusters, potentially obscuring absolute-time microstructure effects such as high-frequency latency arbitrage.

Sentiment Classification Limitations

Despite its structural advantages, the NLI-based framework presents several constraints. First, the SNLI/MNLI training corpora are not domain-specific to financial or prediction market jargon. The presence of platform-specific slang, irony, or heavy sarcasm introduces classification noise due to domain shift. Second, NLI models evaluate text strictly at the sentence-pair level and struggle with implicit reasoning that requires broader conversational or historical context. Comments relying heavily on shared community knowledge exhibit weak signals, resulting in misclassifications as “Neutral”. Moreover, the vertical clustering exhibited suggests the NLI framework compresses much of the signal into narrow bands, limiting meaningful variation. This compression weakens the ability to detect a reliable relationship between stated conviction and realized trading edge. Finally, cross-encoder inference is computationally intensive compared to embedding-based methods, making the processing of millions of live comments highly demanding on distributed inference infrastructure. While Large Language Models (LLMs) present a theoretical alternative, their inference latency and per-call expense currently make large-scale or real-time deployment materially more costly.

Data Coverage, Quality, and Reliability Limitations

While the dataset utilized in this study is substantial, it is constrained by market breadth and platform-specific data reliability issues (see Appendix B). Prediction markets exhibit a high rate of event turnover, meaning our sample captures only a specific slice of market behavior. Furthermore, our dataset lacks dimensionality regarding the underlying reference events (e.g., live sports scores or asset prices), limiting our ability to control for real-world catalysts over the contract lifecycle and preventing direct examination of broader, event-level behavioral dynamics.

Additionally, our reliance on backfilled historical snapshots rather than live WebSocket-based streaming introduces potential inconsistencies and missing observations across trades, order book snapshots, and comments, while also creating a dependence on third-party APIs such as Predexon, whose stability is uncertain. Accessing historical data via APIs for closed markets revealed several data-quality issues: the Dome API experienced pagination errors that likely resulted in missing pages of historical trade data; the Kalshi API does not include trade direction labels (i.e., BUY or SELL) in its historical endpoints despite displaying them on its interface; and comments returned through the Polymarket API are not exhaustive.

Future Work

Building upon the anomalies uncovered and the limitations identified in this study, several promising avenues for future research emerge to refine, validate, and extend these findings:

- Broad-Spectrum Methodological Validation:** Crucially, the behavioral findings presented in this paper—most notably the re-characterization of the favorite-longshot bias as a temporal “Yes Bias” [1] in Mention Markets, and the structural underperformance of highly capitalized “Whales”—are derived from a novel, high-resolution continuous methodology. Because these results challenge established behavioral finance assumptions, they require extensive replication. Future research should apply this framework to even larger datasets with diverse event types and longer time horizons, covering distinct macroeconomic regimes. Additionally, employing alternative non-parametric estimators—such as Gaussian Processes or Kernel Smoothing—will help ensure these patterns are fundamental market mechanics rather than artifacts of the spline architecture.
- Transitioning to Multi-Dimensional Regime Models:** To address the limitations of additive smooths, future work should employ full 2D tensor-product interactions ($s(\text{price}, \text{time})$) to map the joint execution surface. This would allow researchers to investigate if the non-linear coupling of bias and edge is exacerbated at specific liquidity windows (e.g., market open vs. expiration) or if extreme longshots exhibit different temporal decay patterns than favorites. Because higher-dimensional tensor products severely elevate the likelihood of overfitting, future implementations will require aggressive regularization strategies to maintain mathematical stability near the sparse absolute probability tails.
- Liquidity-Weighted Edge and Microstructure:** To account for varying market depth, future studies should incorporate order book snapshots directly into the regression framework. By weighting observed edge by the prevailing bid-ask spread and available depth at the time of execution, researchers can determine whether Whale underperformance is a result of pure ideological mispricing or a structural cost of liquidity provision in thin markets.
- Data Pipeline Enhancements and On-Chain Reconstruction:** Future data collection should transition to fully live WebSocket-based streaming to enhance reliability, granularity, and timeliness, eliminating reliance on third-party snapshot APIs (though limited to active markets). For historical data, to avoid reliance on third-party APIs for Polymarket trades data, researchers should reconstruct maker and taker addresses directly from on-chain data. Furthermore, missing/incomplete data fields—such as Kalshi trade directions and Polymarket comments—should be recovered through direct web scraping.
- Context-Aware and LLM-Based Stance Detection:** To overcome the domain-shift and context limitations of general NLI models, future research should leverage prompt-engineered Large Language Models (LLMs) to perform stance classification. By providing the LLM with the trader’s current position and the recent history of

community discourse, researchers can capture the implicit logical nuances and sarcasm that define prediction market social dynamics. Furthermore, future research should integrate comment reaction data (i.e. "likes" on Polymarket comments, which our tool collects) to gauge how aligned the broader community is with the vocal direction of a specific trader.

- **Behavioral Classification via Reference-Event Data:** Future research should increase the dimensionality of the dataset by incorporating live information on underlying reference events (e.g., score differentials and time remaining in sports, contemporaneous price and volatility in crypto, or intraday S&P index levels). Integrating this context would allow researchers to classify bias in terms of specific behavioral mechanisms—such as overreaction or underreaction to news—moving beyond aggregate price deviations to identify distinct informational drivers.
- **Cross-Asset Integration and Hedging:** Our analysis of 15M Crypto Markets revealed unique efficiency dynamics likely stemming from participants anchoring to external order books. Future studies should map the transmission of price shocks between a primary asset (e.g., Bitcoin spot) and its derivative prediction market, investigating whether the "edge" captured by certain participants is actually a risk premium paid by institutional actors dynamically hedging real-world portfolios.

Appendix A

The System Design In More Detail

The system's entry point utilizes a **Fluent Builder Pattern** to guarantee configuration safety.

- **MarketHandler & RealMarketHandler**: The handler dynamically prompts for required API keys (Kalshi, Polymarket, Dome, Predexon) using auto-generated type stubs (`gen_stubs.py`). Once validated, it instantiates the `RealMarketHandler`, which maintains a dictionary of active threads (`trackers`) and their statuses (`TrackerStatus`).
- **config.py**: Acts as a centralized, thread-safe memory store for runtime configuration and API keys, shielding the core logic from direct environment variable dependencies.

A.1 The Market Interface

All market trackers inherit from the abstract base class `MarketInterface`. This class defines the lifecycle of a market tracker and orchestrates the boundary between networking and persistence.

A.1.1 Tracker Lifecycle

The `run()` method defines a strict lifecycle for every spawned event and market thread:

1. **Verification (`verify()`)**: Validates the provided URL representing an event or market, fetches event/market metadata via REST, and instantiates event and related markets objects
2. **Backfilling (`backfill_all()`)**: Fetches historical trades, L1/L2 order book snapshots, and comments via REST APIs.
3. **Persistence Initialization**: Spawns a dedicated background `db_thread` that continuously reads from a thread-safe data queue.
4. **Live Streaming (`_start_streams()`)**: Enters an `asyncio` event loop, using `asyncio.gather` to concurrently listen to WebSockets for trades, order books, comments, and market

resolutions (when a final price is assigned to each outcome of a market).

A.2 Data Normalization (Data Types)

To support cross-platform analysis and seamlessly switch between backfilled data and live streamed data, the system normalizes all incoming data into strict `dataclass` representations (`data_types.py`):

- **ParentEvent & TickerInfo**: Hierarchical metadata distinguishing between a broad event (e.g., “Next President”) and a tradable market (e.g., “Trump - Yes or No”).
- **TradeData**: Captures executions, explicitly tagging `maker_address` and `taker_address` for Polymarket trades.
- **L1Data & L2Data**: Represents the Top-of-Book (Best Bid/Ask and Spread) and full depth-of-book levels (`Level` object).
- **CommentData & ReactionData**: Captures social sentiment, mapping users to their specific comments and current position snapshots.

A.3 Data Persistence Layer

The database layer (`db.py`) is highly optimized to handle the mismatch between rapid asynchronous network reads and synchronous disk writes. Crucially, it is designed around an abstract interface that prioritizes modularity, making it trivial to scale from local files to cloud databases.

A.3.1 Database Extensibility via Abstract Interfaces

At the core of the persistence layer is the `DatabaseClient(ABC)` abstract base class. This design completely decouples the market trackers from the underlying storage mechanism. Any new database implementation (e.g., PostgreSQL, Supabase, MySQL) only needs to subclass `DatabaseClient` and implement an `insert_batch()` method. Because the system inherently normalizes all event and market representations into Python `dataclasses`, migrating to a new SQL schema or cloud provider requires zero changes to the core WebSocket or REST tracking logic.

A.3.2 Concurrency Strategies: Multiton vs. Write-Ahead Logging (WAL)

SQLite traditionally struggles with concurrent writes from multiple threads. To solve this without sacrificing throughput, the architecture provides two interchangeable SQLite implementations depending on deployment needs:

- **AsyncSQLiteClient (The Multiton Single-Writer)**: This implementation implements a Multiton pattern. If 50 trackers are instantiated for the same database file, they all receive a reference to the *exact same* instance. This instance uses a strict

`threading.Lock()`, ensuring that only one writer thread ever touches the SQLite file at any given moment. This option is better for tracking one or two markets with high data reliability.

- **LocalSQLiteClient (WAL-Mode Multithreading):** As a highly concurrent alternative, this client leverages SQLite’s Write-Ahead Logging mechanism (`PRAGMA journal_mode=WAL;`). Instead of enforcing a global application lock, it opens and closes independent database connections for each batch write. This delegates concurrency control to the OS and SQLite’s internal WAL manager, allowing multiple threads to write simultaneously without blocking readers or corrupting the database. This option is better for tracking many markets with high throughput, but may result in data corruption if the server loses power.

A.3.3 BatchWriter (Dynamic EMA Batching)

Data is not written row-by-row. Instead, the `BatchWriter` buffers data using **Dynamic Exponential Moving Average (EMA) Batching**, which acts as the bridge between the high-frequency trackers and the database clients.

- **Dynamic Sizing:** If the observed flow rate of incoming data increases (e.g., high volatility causing rapid L2 updates), the `BatchWriter` calculates the ratio of elapsed time to the target interval, smoothing it via an EMA. It dynamically increases the `batch_size` to maintain optimal disk I/O target intervals, preventing the database from bottlenecking the network stream.
- **Staleness Flush:** If a market goes quiet (e.g., an illiquid market or sparse comment stream), a `flush_if_stale` mechanism forces a database commit based on maximum age. This ensures crucial but infrequent data isn’t trapped in RAM indefinitely awaiting a full batch.

A.4 Platform-Specific Implementations

Because Polymarket and Kalshi rely on distinct data sources, each platform is implemented through its own class interface—`PolymarketTracker` and `KalshiTracker`—both of which inherit from the abstract base class `MarketInterface`. Additional details regarding platform-specific data sourcing are provided in Appendix B. This modular design enables straightforward extension to other prediction market platforms: incorporating a new platform requires only the implementation of a new class inheriting from `MarketInterface` and the definition of the corresponding abstract methods.

Appendix B

Polymarket and Kalshi Data: Structure and Caveats

B.1 Trades

For Polymarket trades data, we used Dome API because it enriches the Polymarket API trades response with information about the maker and taker of each trade. An issue we noticed with the Dome API was that it would occasionally return an invalid pagination key. Thus, there may be data reliability issues with using Dome (i.e. potentially missed pages of trades). Live trades were streamed via the Dome WebSocket.

We used the Kalshi API for Kalshi trades data. However, unlike the Polymarket trades data, Kalshi does not provide information about the maker or taker, which exempted Kalshi from a lot of our research. Furthermore, Kalshi trades data does not include the direction of the trade (i.e. BUY or SELL). Thus, for Kalshi trades, we assumed each trade represented a BUY from the taker. Because of this assumption, analysis of Kalshi markets was exempt from Chapter 3.3. Live trades were streamed via the Kalshi WebSocket.

B.2 Order Book Snapshots

For Polymarket historical L1 and L2 order book snapshots, we used Dome API since the Polymarket API doesn't offer this data. Polymarket provides order book snapshots on both outcomes of a given market. We noticed that with Polymarket historical order book data, there are some markets where there are trades history, but not order book snapshots. Live order book snapshots were streamed from the Polymarket Websocket.

Kalshi's historical L1 and L2 order book snapshots were retrieved from the Predexon API, because the Kalshi API does not offer historical order book data. Unlike Polymarket, Kalshi only provides order book snapshots for one outcome per market. However, it is easy to reconstruct the corresponding orderbook snapshot for the other outcome - for some level l

of the order book, the following holds:

$$\begin{cases} \text{Price}_{\text{ask},l,\text{Outcome A}} = 1 - \text{Price}_{\text{bid},l,\text{Outcome B}} \\ \text{Size}_{\text{ask},l,\text{Outcome A}} = \text{Size}_{\text{bid},l,\text{Outcome B}} \end{cases}$$

These relationships also hold for the Polymarket order book snapshots.

A limitation of the historical order book snapshots obtained from both Kalshi and Polymarket is that their timestamps do not align with trade timestamps and that they are recorded at a substantially lower frequency, making it difficult to accurately match trades to prevailing liquidity conditions. Consequently, analyses based on mid quotes rather than transaction prices substantially reduce the effective sample size. While the issue of infrequent snapshots can be mitigated for live markets by streaming data during active trading rather than relying on historical API snapshots, it cannot be resolved for markets that have already closed.

Live order book snapshots were streamed through the Kalshi WebSocket. Because the WebSocket streams orderbook *deltas*, an internal state machine applies mathematical deltas to fixed-point price levels, generating new order book snapshots upon every tick.

B.3 Comments

Historical comments data is only retrievable via API for Polymarket, not for Kalshi. Live comments data is streamed through the Polymarket WebSocket. It is important to note that for Polymarket, unlike trades and order book snapshots, comments are stored at the event or series level, not the market level. A caveat of the comments data returned by the Polymarket API is that it is highly unreliable and often non-exhaustive, at times returning only a subset of the total comments. For example, for events with more than 30 comments (as verified on the website), requesting 30 comments via the API may yield only 10. This inconsistency can materially reduce the effective sample size of collected comments and may result in missing observations at particular stages of the event lifecycle. Streaming comments can mitigate this, but only for active markets.

Appendix C

Data Structures

To enable robust, cross-platform analysis of prediction markets, the system normalizes highly fragmented JSON payloads from Polymarket and Kalshi into a strictly typed, relational database schema. The persistence layer outputs a localized SQLite database (or scalable cloud equivalent) consisting of seven primary tables. These tables are conceptually divided into three tiers: Hierarchical Metadata, Market Microstructure, and Social Sentiment.

A Note on Nomenclature: Throughout the body of this paper, we utilize standard industry terminology, referring to broad questions as “*events*” and the specific, mutually exclusive tradable contracts as “*markets*.” However, to maintain strict alignment with the system’s underlying code architecture, the database layer utilizes the terms `parent_events` and `tickers`, respectively.

C.0.1 Hierarchical Metadata

Prediction markets fundamentally operate on a parent-child hierarchy. A broad question constitutes the “Parent Event,” while the specific tradable contracts constitute the “Tickers.”

Table: `parent_events`

This table captures the overarching market narrative and metadata. It acts as the anchor for all subsequent relational joins.

Column	Type	Description
<code>id</code>	TEXT (PK)	Unique identifier.
<code>slug</code>	TEXT	Unique string identifier.
<code>name</code>	TEXT	The plain English question (e.g., “Next US President?”).
<code>has_multiple_tickers</code>	BOOLEAN	True if the event has more than 1 market.
<code>start_timestamp</code>	TEXT	ISO8601 timestamp of market creation.
<code>end_timestamp</code>	TEXT	ISO8601 timestamp of scheduled resolution.
<code>description</code>	TEXT	Description of the event.
<code>platform</code>	TEXT	Source platform (Polymarket or Kalshi).
<code>metadata</code>	TEXT	Miscellaneous information, such as the market category.

Table C.1: Schema for `parent_events`

Table: ticker_info

This table defines the actual tradable contracts (children) linked to a parent event. It tracks the outcome options and the final resolved state of the market.

Column	Type	Description
<code>ticker_id</code>	TEXT (PK)	Unique identifier for the tradable contract.
<code>parent_event_id</code>	TEXT (FK)	Foreign key linking to <code>parent_events.id</code> .
<code>ticker_name</code>	TEXT	The specific contract name (e.g., “Donald Trump”).
<code>platform_id</code>	TEXT	Source platform.
<code>outcome_options</code>	TEXT	Tuple string of tradable outcomes (e.g., “[‘Yes’, ‘No’]”).
<code>start_timestamp</code>	TEXT	ISO8601 timestamp when the ticker begins trading.
<code>end_timestamp</code>	TEXT	ISO8601 timestamp when a resolution price is determined.
<code>description</code>	TEXT	Full contextual description of the contract and resolution rules.
<code>metadata</code>	TEXT	Miscellaneous platform-specific IDs relevant to the market, e.g. Polymarket <code>clobTokenIds</code> .
<code>outcome</code>	TEXT	The final resolved state of the ticker (NULL while active).

Table C.2: Schema for `ticker_info`

C.0.2 Market Microstructure

The microstructure tables form the core of the dataset.

Table: trades

This table records every matched execution on the order book. Crucially, the system enriches standard trade data by extracting the cryptographic `maker_address` and `taker_address` where possible, allowing for wallet-level behavioral profiling.

Column	Type	Description
<code>trade_id</code>	TEXT (PK)	Unique transaction or execution hash.
<code>parent_event_id</code>	TEXT	Link to the parent event.
<code>ticker_id</code>	TEXT (FK)	The contract being traded.
<code>platform_id</code>	TEXT	Source platform.
<code>timestamp</code>	TEXT	Millisecond-precision execution time (UTC).
<code>price</code>	REAL	The matched price (between 0 and 1).
<code>size</code>	REAL	The number of shares/contracts exchanged.
<code>side</code>	TEXT	The aggressive side of the trade (BUY or SELL).
<code>outcome</code>	TEXT	The specific outcome purchased (e.g., “Yes”).
<code>maker_address</code>	TEXT	Identifier of the limit order maker.
<code>taker_address</code>	TEXT	Identifier of the market order taker.
<code>metadata</code>	TEXT	Additional trade metadata.

Table C.3: Schema for `trades`

Table: `l1_data` (Top of Book)

The Level 1 (L1) table tracks the Best Bid and Best Offer (BBO).

Column	Type	Description
<code>parent_event_id</code>	TEXT	Link to the parent event.
<code>ticker_id</code>	TEXT (FK)	The contract identifier.
<code>platform_id</code>	TEXT	Source platform.
<code>timestamp</code>	TEXT	Time of the top-of-book update.
<code>best_bid</code>	TEXT	JSON string containing price and resting size.
<code>best_ask</code>	TEXT	JSON string containing price and resting size.
<code>outcome</code>	TEXT	Indicates which outcome’s perspective the book reflects.
<code>metadata</code>	TEXT	Optional metadata.
<code>spread</code>	REAL	The mathematical difference between best ask and best bid.

Table C.4: Schema for `l1_data` (Top of Book)

Table: 12_data (Depth of Book)

The Level 2 (L2) table stores full depth-of-book snapshots. Tracking the resting liquidity beyond the best bid/ask allows researchers to measure the market impact of hypothetical large orders and observe market maker wall placements.

Column	Type	Description
parent_event_id	TEXT	Link to the parent event.
ticker_id	TEXT (FK)	The contract identifier.
platform_id	TEXT	Source platform.
timestamp	TEXT	Time of the depth update/snapshot.
bids	TEXT	Serialized JSON array of [price, size] Level objects.
asks	TEXT	Serialized JSON array of [price, size] Level objects.
outcome	TEXT	Indicates which outcome's perspective the book reflects.
metadata	TEXT	Optional metadata.

Table C.5: Schema for 12_data (Depth of Book)

C.0.3 Social Sentiment

To correlate price action with social momentum, the system captures real-time comment data, user reactions, and snapshot estimations of commenters' financial exposure.

Table: comments

Column	Type	Description
comment_id	TEXT (PK)	Unique comment identifier.
parent_event_id	TEXT (FK)	The event being discussed.
ticker_id	TEXT	Specific ticker being referenced (if applicable).
platform_id	TEXT	Source platform.
timestamp	TEXT	Time the comment was made.
user_id	TEXT	Unique identifier of the user/wallet.
user_name	TEXT	Display name of the user.
text	TEXT	The payload of the comment.
metadata	TEXT	Raw JSON snapshot for platform specifics.
outcome	TEXT	The outcome the user's position supports.
user_tags	TEXT	Behavioral tags applied by the platform (e.g., "Whale").
user_position_snapshot	TEXT	JSON serialization of the user's active portfolio.
reply_to_id	TEXT	Relational ID mapping this to a previous comment.

Table C.6: Schema for `comments`

Table: reactions

This table captures granular engagement metrics on individual comments, mapping sentiment shifts across the user base.

Column	Type	Description
reaction_id	TEXT (PK)	Unique reaction identifier.
comment_id	TEXT (FK)	Links to <code>comments.comment_id</code> .
user_address	TEXT	Identifier of the user reacting to the comment.
reaction.type	TEXT	Classification of engagement (e.g., "like", "dislike").
timestamp	TEXT	Time the reaction was recorded.
platform_id	TEXT	Source platform.

Table C.7: Schema for `reactions`

Appendix D

Supplemental Data Quality Plots and Significance Tests

To ensure the robustness of our spline regressions and to transparently document the support of our data across different regimes, we present the absolute trade count distributions over both implied probability (price) and normalized time.

(a) 15M Crypto Markets

(b) Mention Markets

(c) NBA Markets

Figure D.1: Distribution of absolute trade counts across implied probability (Price) for different market categories. Notice the highly bimodal distribution in Mention Markets and 15M Crypto Markets, underscoring the necessity of penalized smoothing in sparse middle-probability regions.

(a) 15M Crypto Markets

(b) Mention Markets

(c) NBA Markets

Figure D.2: Distribution of absolute trade counts across normalized contract lifecycle (Time). Across all market types, trading volume exhibits a massive spike as time approaches 1.0 (resolution), confirming the heavy late-stage liquidity dynamics that confound univariate price models.

Table D.1: An overview of our significance tests and P-values. *** = 1%, ** = 5%, and * = 10%. Some tests were not included in this paper.

db	question	model	test	stat	df	p_value	target	null_hyp	sig	stars
Polymarket_15M	Q1_bias_mean	descriptive	mean_test	-0.091200		0.927300	bias	E[bias]=0	ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q10_comment_interaction_joint	spline	wald_test	45.874300	48.000000	0.560400			ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q10_comment_main_effect	spline	wald_test	-0.559700	1.000000	0.575700	comment_main_effect	comment coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q10_comment_x_price_spline_block	spline	wald_test	24.681400	24.000000	0.423200			ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q10_comment_x_time_spline_block	spline	wald_test	17.204800	24.000000	0.839800			ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q2_bias_vs_price	quantile_bin	wald_test	108.497600	91.000000	0.101900	price_spline_block	all price terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q2_bias_vs_price	spline	wald_test	32.832500	24.000000	0.107700	price_spline_block	all price terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q3_bias_vs_time	quantile_bin	wald_test	111.266500	99.000000	0.188100	time_spline_block	all time terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q3_bias_vs_time	spline	wald_test	31.522900	24.000000	0.139300	time_spline_block	all time terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q4_taker_edge_vs_price	spline	wald_test	56.643700	48.000000	0.183700	price_spline_block	all price terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q4_taker_edge_vs_time	spline	wald_test	31.930900	48.000000	0.964100	time_spline_block	all time terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_15M	Q5_Anderson_Darling_k_sample	distribution_test	Anderson_Darling_k_sample	928.839400		0.000000	maker_vs_taker_distribution	maker and taker unit-edge distributions are equal	1%	***
Polymarket_15M	Q5_KS	distribution_test	KS	0.068000		0.000000	maker_vs_taker_distribution	maker and taker unit-edge distributions are equal	1%	***

Continued on next page

Table D.1: An overview of our significance tests and P-values. *** = 1%, ** = 5%, and * = 10%. Some tests were not included in this paper.

db	question	model	test	stat	df	p_value	target	null_hyp	sig	stars
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	Q6_edge_vs_ participant_size_pct	spline	wald_test	44.280100	24.000000	0.007100	participant_ size_block	all participant size terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	Q7_whale_main_effect	spline	wald_test	60.514700	49.000000	0.125300	whale_main_ effect	whale coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	Q8_whale_ interaction_joint	spline	wald_test	52.117800	48.000000	0.316900	whale_x_price_ time_joint	all whale interaction terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	Q8_whale_x_price_ spline_block	spline	wald_test	28.379700	24.000000	0.244300	whale_x_price_ block	all whale x price terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	Q8_whale_x_time_ spline_block	spline	wald_test	18.926000	24.000000	0.755900	whale_x_time_ block	all whale x time terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q1_bias_mean	descriptive	mean_test	-1.701300		0.088900	bias	E[bias]=0	10%	*
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q10_comment_ interaction_joint	spline	wald_test	60.997500	48.000000	0.098600			10%	*
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q10_comment_main_ effect	spline	wald_test	-0.049400	1.000000	0.960600	comment_ main_effect	comment coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q10_comment_x_ price_spline_block	spline	wald_test	18.596300	24.000000	0.773200			ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q10_comment_x_ time_spline_block	spline	wald_test	34.135000	24.000000	0.082300			10%	*
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q2_bias_vs_price	quantile_ bin	wald_test	337.429500	89.000000	0.000000	price_spline_ block	all price terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q2_bias_vs_price	spline	wald_test	78.660300	24.000000	0.000000	price_spline_ block	all price terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q3_bias_vs_time	quantile_ bin	wald_test	260.453800	97.000000	0.000000	time_spline_ block	all time terms = 0	1%	***

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Table D.1: An overview of our significance tests and P-values. *** = 1%, ** = 5%, and * = 10%. Some tests were not included in this paper.

db	question	model	test	stat	df	p_value	target	null_hyp	sig	stars
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q3_bias_vs_time	spline	wald_test	89.081000	24.000000	0.000000	time_spline_ block	all time terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q4_taker_edge_vs_ price	spline	wald_test	132.822900	48.000000	0.000000	price_spline_ block	all price terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q4_taker_edge_vs_ time	spline	wald_test	92.611100	48.000000	0.000100	time_spline_ block	all time terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q5_Anderson_ Darling_k_sample	distribution_ test	Anderson_ Darling_k_ sample	3.801400		0.000100	maker_vs_ taker_ distribution	maker and taker unit-edge distributions are equal	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q5_KS	distribution_ test	KS	0.029900		0.066700	maker_vs_ taker_ distribution	maker and taker unit-edge distributions are equal	10%	*
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q6_edge_vs_ participant_size_pct	spline	wald_test	55.920800	24.000000	0.000200	participant_ size_block	all participant size terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q7_whale_main_effect	spline	wald_test	140.260900	49.000000	0.000000	whale_main_ effect	whale coefficient = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q8_whale_ interaction_joint	spline	wald_test	126.239900	48.000000	0.000000	whale_x_price_ time_joint	all whale interaction terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q8_whale_x_price_ spline_block	spline	wald_test	45.836100	24.000000	0.004600	whale_x_price_ block	all whale x price terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	Q8_whale_x_time_ spline_block	spline	wald_test	55.897300	24.000000	0.000200	whale_x_time_ block	all whale x time terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q1_bias_mean	descriptive	mean_test	0.875300		0.381400	bias	E[bias]=0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q10_comment_ interaction_joint	spline	wald_test	41.762400	48.000000	0.725000			ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q10_comment_main_ effect	spline	wald_test	-0.341500	1.000000	0.732700	comment_ main_effect	comment coefficient = 0	ns	

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Table D.1: An overview of our significance tests and P-values. *** = 1%, ** = 5%, and * = 10%. Some tests were not included in this paper.

db	question	model	test	stat	df	p_value	target	null_hyp	sig	stars
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q10_comment_x_ price_spline_block	spline	wald_test	17.860100	24.000000	0.809700			ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q10_comment_x_ time_spline_block	spline	wald_test	26.334500	24.000000	0.336400			ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q2_bias_vs_price	quantile_ bin	wald_test	103.129900	56.000000	0.000100	price_spline_ block	all price terms = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q2_bias_vs_price	spline	wald_test	26.732500	24.000000	0.317100	price_spline_ block	all price terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q3_bias_vs_time	quantile_ bin	wald_test	124.999400	93.000000	0.015100	time_spline_ block	all time terms = 0	5%	**
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q3_bias_vs_time	spline	wald_test	29.483200	24.000000	0.202500	time_spline_ block	all time terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q4_taker_edge_vs_ price	spline	wald_test	44.458300	48.000000	0.618800	price_spline_ block	all price terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q4_taker_edge_vs_ time	spline	wald_test	52.958900	48.000000	0.288700	time_spline_ block	all time terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q5_Anderson_ Darling_k_sample	distribution_ test	Anderson_ Darling_k_ sample	25.170400		0.000000	maker_vs_ taker_ distribution	maker and taker unit-edge distributions are equal	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q5_KS	distribution_ test	KS	0.033400		0.000000	maker_vs_ taker_ distribution	maker and taker unit-edge distributions are equal	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q6_edge_vs_ participant_size_pct	spline	wald_test	14.879500	24.000000	0.924200	participant_ size_block	all participant size terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q7_whale_main_effect	spline	wald_test	89.616900	49.000000	0.000400	whale_main_ effect	whale coefficient = 0	1%	***
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q8_whale_ interaction_joint	spline	wald_test	69.553000	48.000000	0.022600	whale_x_price_ time_joint	all whale interaction terms = 0	5%	**

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Table D.1: An overview of our significance tests and P-values. *** = 1%, ** = 5%, and * = 10%. Some tests were not included in this paper.

db	question	model	test	stat	df	p_value	target	null_hyp	sig	stars
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q8_whale_x_price_ spline_block	spline	wald_test	32.080900	24.000000	0.125000	whale_x_price_ block	all whale x price terms = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ NBA	Q8_whale_x_time_ spline_block	spline	wald_test	38.425600	24.000000	0.031300	whale_x_time_ block	all whale x time terms = 0	5%	**
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	SentimentEdge	model_1_ linear_ sentiment	regression	0.028939	1	0.8649	has_comment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	SentimentEdge	model_1_ linear_ sentiment	regression	0.052902	1	0.8181	hc_x_sentiment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	SentimentEdge	model_3_ three_ bins	regression	0.089804	1	0.7644	has_comment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	SentimentEdge	model_3_ three_ bins	regression		1		hc_x_S_pos	coefficient = 0		
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	SentimentEdge	model_3_ three_ bins	regression	0.000000	2		hc_x_S_pos_neg_joi	joint coeffs = 0		
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	SentimentEdge	model_4_ binary_ sign	regression	0.077517	1	0.7807	has_comment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ 15M	SentimentEdge	model_4_ binary_ sign	regression	0.106048	1	0.7447	hc_x_is_S_pos	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	SentimentEdge	model_1_ linear_ sentiment	regression	2.243402	1	0.1342	has_comment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	SentimentEdge	model_1_ linear_ sentiment	regression	2.214860	1	0.1367	hc_x_sentiment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_ Markets_ MentionMarkets	SentimentEdge	model_3_ three_ bins	regression	2.248939	1	0.1337	has_comment	coefficient = 0	ns	

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Table D.1: An overview of our significance tests and P-values. *** = 1%, ** = 5%, and * = 10%. Some tests were not included in this paper.

db	question	model	test	stat	df	p_value	target	null_hyp	sig	stars
Polymarket_Markets_MentionMarkets	SentimentEdge	model_3_three_bins	regression		1		hc_x_S_pos	coefficient = 0		
Polymarket_Markets_MentionMarkets	SentimentEdge	model_3_three_bins	regression		1		hc_x_S_neg	coefficient = 0		
Polymarket_Markets_MentionMarkets	SentimentEdge	model_3_three_bins	regression	0.000000	2		hc_x_S_pos_neg_joint	joint coeffs = 0		
Polymarket_Markets_MentionMarkets	SentimentEdge	model_4_binary_sign	regression	4.206906	1	0.0403	has_comment	coefficient = 0	5%	**
Polymarket_Markets_MentionMarkets	SentimentEdge	model_4_binary_sign	regression	2.374151	1	0.1234	hc_x_is_S_pos	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_Markets_NBA	SentimentEdge	model_1_linear_sentiment	regression	0.285224	1	0.5933	has_comment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_Markets_NBA	SentimentEdge	model_1_linear_sentiment	regression	0.001752	1	0.9666	hc_x_sentiment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_Markets_NBA	SentimentEdge	model_3_three_bins	regression	0.284759	1	0.5936	has_comment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_Markets_NBA	SentimentEdge	model_3_three_bins	regression		1		hc_x_S_pos	coefficient = 0		
Polymarket_Markets_NBA	SentimentEdge	model_3_three_bins	regression		1		hc_x_S_neg	coefficient = 0		
Polymarket_Markets_NBA	SentimentEdge	model_3_three_bins	regression	0.000000	2		hc_x_S_pos_neg_joint	joint coeffs = 0		
Polymarket_Markets_NBA	SentimentEdge	model_4_binary_sign	regression	0.295860	1	0.5865	has_comment	coefficient = 0	ns	
Polymarket_Markets_NBA	SentimentEdge	model_4_binary_sign	regression	0.122899	1	0.7259	hc_x_is_S_pos	coefficient = 0	ns	

Table D.2: Polymarket Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles: 15M Crypto Markets (Volume)

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	-0.015399 (0.043725)	-0.027324 (0.026036)	-0.017355 (0.027472)	0.027341 (0.034898)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	0.005495 (0.045773)	-0.025527 (0.039245)	0.006874 (0.042465)	0.061256 (0.052104)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	-0.005861 (0.025252)	0.012457 (0.029145)	-0.003046 (0.037422)	-0.070675 (0.057479)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	-0.009233 (0.041810)	0.027625 (0.040765)	-0.017416 (0.038857)	-0.026156 (0.048536)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	0.032329 (0.043906)	0.003661 (0.036056)	-0.016403 (0.032658)	0.038123* (0.014348)
Small Probabilities	-0.004952 (0.037066)	-0.026425 (0.028667)	-0.005240 (0.029089)	0.044298 (0.036304)
Large Probabilities	0.005745 (0.028570)	0.014581 (0.025463)	-0.012288 (0.026719)	-0.019569 (0.032258)
Large – Small	0.010697 (0.047384)	0.041006 (0.036101)	-0.007048 (0.035376)	-0.063868 (0.041729)
R^2	0.000250	0.002124	0.000535	0.013756
Expiration Days	110	109	108	93
Observations	401,217	401,217	401,217	401,217

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Figure D.3: Liquidity and Favorite-Longshot Bias: Polymarket 15M Crypto Markets

Table D.3: Polymarket Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles: NBA Markets (Volume)

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
0.00 ≤ Price < 0.20	-0.107209*** (0.030974)	-0.103791*** (0.031403)	-0.003037 (0.044985)	-0.032873 (0.025223)
0.20 ≤ Price < 0.40	-0.022998 (0.092739)	0.017737 (0.104301)	0.112372 (0.089525)	0.001488 (0.055220)
0.40 ≤ Price < 0.60	-0.000474 (0.033450)	0.001519 (0.074805)	0.049522 (0.082259)	0.037106 (0.067727)
0.60 ≤ Price < 0.80	0.033520 (0.057297)	0.043724 (0.064592)	-0.010089 (0.107256)	0.180236*** (0.045656)
0.80 ≤ Price < 1.00	0.082445 (0.051124)	0.083110 (0.068968)	0.051161 (0.037344)	0.031332 (0.044129)
Small Probabilities	-0.065103 (0.054037)	-0.043027 (0.058836)	0.054667 (0.059204)	-0.015693 (0.033226)
Large Probabilities	0.038497 (0.033054)	0.042784 (0.046066)	0.030198 (0.057919)	0.082891* (0.044903)
Large – Small	0.103600 (0.070520)	0.085811 (0.083901)	-0.024469 (0.085888)	0.098584* (0.054267)
R^2	0.006216	0.010765	0.011353	0.030902
Expiration Days	38	33	29	26
Observations	158,975	158,975	158,974	158,975

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table D.4: Polymarket Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles: Mention Markets (Volume)

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
0.00 ≤ Price < 0.20	-0.031485*** (0.002710)	-0.024993*** (0.004292)	-0.017745 (0.014050)	-0.025004*** (0.003935)
0.20 ≤ Price < 0.40	-0.096667 (0.071490)	-0.350714*** (0.000000)	0 (0.000000)	0 (0.000000)
0.40 ≤ Price < 0.60	-0.446667*** (0.086830)	-0.224091 (0.221295)	-0.345000*** (0.080990)	0 (0.000000)
0.60 ≤ Price < 0.80	0.029710 (0.117793)	0.270833*** (0.005802)	0.170625*** (0.055823)	0 (0.103397)
0.80 ≤ Price < 1.00	0.016219 (0.066827)	0.067154** (0.026156)	0.067330*** (0.022118)	0.079891** (0.040721)
Small Probabilities	-0.064076* (0.036584)	-0.187854*** (0.002146)	-0.008872 (0.007025)	-0.012502*** (0.001968)
Large Probabilities	-0.133579*** (0.051043)	0.037966 (0.074943)	-0.035682 (0.038654)	0.026630 (0.025926)
Large – Small	-0.069503 (0.068028)	0.225819*** (0.075046)	-0.026809 (0.039757)	0.039132 (0.025986)
R^2	0.096131	0.654317	0.270580	0.141804
Expiration Days	13	13	14	10
Observations	432	431	431	432

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table D.5: Kalshi 15M Crypto Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles (Volume)

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	0.057773 (0.053772)	-0.036079 (0.045604)	-0.061592*** (0.020567)	-0.048189** (0.023008)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	-0.053705 (0.108575)	-0.056947 (0.075323)	-0.168095*** (0.042792)	-0.070892** (0.034750)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	-0.100857** (0.039322)	-0.076040 (0.077260)	-0.162211*** (0.028624)	-0.071903*** (0.017761)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	-0.045522*** (0.002124)	-0.040296* (0.023530)	-0.020697 (0.017962)	-0.313182*** (0.015164)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	-0.078475*** (0.000000)	-0.039379*** (0.000000)	0.066211*** (0.000677)	0.000052*** (0.000000)
Small Probabilities	0.002034 (0.081174)	-0.046513 (0.060463)	-0.114843*** (0.031679)	-0.059541** (0.028879)
Large Probabilities	-0.074951*** (0.012399)	-0.051905 (0.033597)	-0.038899** (0.015303)	-0.128344*** (0.010975)
Large – Small	-0.076985 (0.068774)	-0.005392 (0.026867)	0.075944*** (0.016376)	-0.068803*** (0.017904)
R^2	0.009372	0.001461	0.037367	0.052602
Expiration Days	2	2	2	2
Observations	1,188,444	1,188,444	1,188,444	1,188,444

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table D.6: Polymarket Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles: 15M Crypto Markets (Depth)

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
0.00 \leq Price < 0.20	0.001697 (0.032310)	-0.006001 (0.033222)	-0.003506 (0.026971)	0.013975 (0.032083)
0.20 \leq Price < 0.40	0.008115 (0.037385)	-0.018554 (0.038549)	0.004526 (0.041748)	0.066415 (0.083123)
0.40 \leq Price < 0.60	-0.031821 (0.037481)	-0.024977 (0.031110)	0.007216 (0.035247)	0.017530 (0.029228)
0.60 \leq Price < 0.80	-0.016919 (0.044472)	-0.037984 (0.039857)	-0.008589 (0.045112)	0.072675 (0.047922)
0.80 \leq Price < 1.00	0.006593 (0.030134)	-0.021983 (0.035048)	0.004382 (0.025440)	0.047611*** (0.009739)
Small Probabilities	0.004906 (0.030066)	-0.012278 (0.031960)	0.000510 (0.029148)	0.040195 (0.053118)
Large Probabilities	-0.014049 (0.032925)	-0.028315 (0.029130)	0.001003 (0.028300)	0.045939** (0.022793)
Large – Small	-0.018955 (0.031554)	-0.016037 (0.038953)	0.000493 (0.032741)	0.005744 (0.051471)
R^2	0.001427	0.000406	0.000202	0.003300
Expiration Days	110	107	107	106
Observations	401,217	401,217	401,217	401,217

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table D.7: Polymarket Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles: NBA Markets (Depth)

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	-0.028707 (0.030339)	0.005015 (0.043817)	-0.084442*** (0.015272)	-0.089311** (0.034782)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	0.021997 (0.089020)	0.031615 (0.065619)	-0.029873 (0.077659)	0.111039 (0.105979)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	0.013328 (0.037209)	0.009855 (0.037269)	0.017363 (0.077308)	0.028554 (0.070449)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	0.063281 (0.047560)	0.071924 (0.044335)	-0.054498 (0.100231)	0.161734*** (0.051560)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	0.044916 (0.031353)	0.016554 (0.044701)	0.062044 (0.046757)	0.090556 (0.058902)
Small Probabilities	-0.003355 (0.054687)	0.018315 (0.048640)	-0.057157 (0.042469)	0.010864 (0.060792)
Large Probabilities	0.040508 (0.028097)	0.032778 (0.032416)	0.008303 (0.048153)	0.093615** (0.044789)
Large – Small	0.043863 (0.061034)	0.014463 (0.058110)	0.065460 (0.067920)	0.082751 (0.083224)
R^2	0.002392	0.002619	0.010101	0.034751
Expiration Days	38	38	38	33
Observations	158,975	158,975	158,974	158,975

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table D.8: Polymarket Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles: Mention Markets (Depth)

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
0.00 ≤ Price < 0.20	-0.026446 (0.017242)	-0.037663*** (0.005139)	-0.018330*** (0.003039)	-0.019830*** (0.002117)
0.20 ≤ Price < 0.40	-0.322121*** (0.005761)	0.605000*** (0.000000)	0 (0.000000)	0 (0.000000)
0.40 ≤ Price < 0.60	0.122500 (0.190050)	-0.561250*** (0.011687)	-0.525000*** (0.018840)	0 (0.000000)
0.60 ≤ Price < 0.80	0.083333 (0.088609)	0.093833* (0.048109)	0.249444*** (0.009648)	0 (0.000000)
0.80 ≤ Price < 1.00	0.047578 (0.040981)	0.058700 (0.041661)	0.093249*** (0.035980)	0.034630*** (0.010754)
Small Probabilities	-0.174284*** (0.009623)	0.283669*** (0.002569)	-0.009165*** (0.001520)	-0.009915*** (0.001058)
Large Probabilities	0.084470 (0.092265)	-0.136239*** (0.023677)	-0.060769*** (0.010744)	0.011543*** (0.003585)
Large – Small	0.258754*** (0.093225)	-0.419908*** (0.023627)	-0.051604*** (0.010802)	0.021458*** (0.003714)
R^2	0.136285	0.412440	0.723974	0.280872
Expiration Days	14	15	14	12
Observations	432	431	431	432

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Table D.9: Kalshi 15M Crypto Favorite-Longshot Bias by Liquidity Quartiles (Depth)

	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
$0.00 \leq \text{Price} < 0.20$	-0.009969 (0.038807)	-0.024942 (0.035426)	-0.014516 (0.047819)	-0.048338** (0.023397)
$0.20 \leq \text{Price} < 0.40$	-0.037433 (0.106304)	-0.081489 (0.071941)	-0.147119*** (0.041891)	-0.100105*** (0.035448)
$0.40 \leq \text{Price} < 0.60$	-0.070412 (0.066656)	-0.136568*** (0.039451)	-0.113428*** (0.026455)	-0.120888*** (0.017869)
$0.60 \leq \text{Price} < 0.80$	-0.021797 (0.026114)	-0.060296*** (0.012093)	-0.143184*** (0.011789)	-0.113097*** (0.001827)
$0.80 \leq \text{Price} < 1.00$	-0.014261*** (0.000655)	-0.032722*** (0.001149)	-0.067759*** (0.000000)	0.022912*** (0.000000)
Small Probabilities	-0.023701 (0.072556)	-0.053216 (0.053684)	-0.080817* (0.044855)	-0.074222** (0.029422)
Large Probabilities	-0.035490 (0.030705)	-0.076529*** (0.016798)	-0.108124*** (0.012748)	-0.070358*** (0.006565)
Large – Small	-0.011789 (0.041850)	-0.023313 (0.036885)	-0.027306 (0.032107)	0.003864 (0.022857)
R^2	0.002423	0.009821	0.010192	0.021020
Expiration Days	2	2	2	2
Observations	1,188,444	1,188,444	1,188,444	1,188,444

Notes: Standard errors are reported in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote statistical significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

Figure D.4: Liquidity and Favorite–Longshot Bias: Polymarket NBA Markets

Figure D.5: Liquidity and Favorite–Longshot Bias: Polymarket Mention Markets

Figure D.6: Liquidity and Favorite–Longshot Bias: Kalshi 15M Crypto Markets

Bibliography

- [1] Bo Cowgill, Justin Wolfers, and Eric Zitzewitz. Using prediction markets to track information flows: Evidence from google. January 2009.
- [2] James Surowiecki. *The Wisdom of Crowds*. Doubleday, New York, 2004.
- [3] Lora Kolodny. How prediction markets work, 2026.
- [4] Business Insider. How hedge funds are using prediction markets data. 2026. Accessed: 2026-02-25.
- [5] Bloomberg. Jump trading poised to gain stakes in kalshi and polymarket. 2026. Accessed: 2026-02-25.
- [6] Anthony M. Diercks, Jonathan D. Katz, and Jonathan H. Wright. Kalshi and the rise of macro markets. Finance and Economics Discussion Series 2026-010, Board of Governors of the Federal Reserve System, 2026.
- [7] Paul C. Tetlock. Liquidity and prediction market efficiency. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 2008.
- [8] Robert Forsythe, Forrest Nelson, George R. Neumann, and Jack Wright. Anatomy of an experimental political stock market. *American Economic Review*, 82:1143–1161, 1992.
- [9] Joyce Berg, Forrest Nelson, and Thomas Rietz. Prediction market accuracy in the long run. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 24:285–300, 2008.
- [10] W. Johansson. Markets vs. machines: An investigation of prediction market forecasting accuracy compared to time series methodologies. *Working Paper*, 2025.
- [11] Justin Wolfers and Eric Zitzewitz. Prediction markets. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 18:107–126, 2004.
- [12] Eric Swanson, Renxuan Wang, and Yanbin Wu. The effects of monetary policy on macroeconomic expectations: High-frequency evidence from traded event contracts. 2025.
- [13] Herman Bergring. Mechanisms, efficiency and probabilistic accuracy of scalable prediction markets. *Bachelor's Thesis, Science and Technology*, 2024.
- [14] Karl Whelan. On prices and returns in commercial prediction markets. 2023.

- [15] Constantin Bürgi, Wanying Deng, and Karl Whelan. Makers and takers: The economics of the kalshi prediction market. *Working Paper*, 2026.
- [16] Felix Reichenbach and Martin Walther. Exploring decentralized prediction markets: Accuracy, skill, and bias on polymarket. 2025.
- [17] Sebastian Bell, Ali Kakhbod, Abdolreza Nazemi, Richard Stanton, and Nancy Wallace. Fairness by design: Machine learning and interpretable mortgage lending. *Working Paper*, 2026. Draft January 2026.
- [18] Sebastian Bell, Ali Kakhbod, Martin Lettau, and Abdolreza Nazemi. Glass box machine learning and corporate bond returns. Working Paper 33320, National Bureau of Economic Research, 2025.
- [19] Ali Kakhbod, Leonid Kogan, Peiyao Li, and Dimitris Papanikolaou. Measuring creative destruction. *Working Paper*, 2025. Draft February 2025.
- [20] Ali Kakhbod, Amir Kermani, and Bernardo Maciel. In the fed’s mind. *Working Paper*, 2025. Draft August 2025.
- [21] Yael V. Hochberg, Ali Kakhbod, Peiyao Li, and Kunal Sachdeva. Are patents with female inventors under-cited? evidence from text estimation. *Working Paper*, 2025.
- [22] Anastassia Fedyk, Ali Kakhbod, Peiyao Li, and Ulrike Malmendier. Ai and perception biases in investments: An experimental study. *Working Paper*, 2025. Draft June 2025.
- [23] Amir Ajorlou, Ali Jadbabaie, and Ali Kakhbod. Dynamic pricing in social networks: The word of mouth effect. *Working Paper*, 2015.
- [24] Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky. Prospect theory: An analysis of decision under risk. *Econometrica*, 47(2):263–291, 1979.
- [25] Drazen Prelec. The probability weighting function. *Econometrica*, 66(3):497–527, 1998.
- [26] Alex Buzunov. Sentence-transformers (sbert) vs cross-encoders: A conceptual guide, September 25 2025.